

1 ***MONOPTEROS* isoform *MP11ir* role during somatic embryogenesis in *Arabidopsis thaliana***

2
3 Barbara Wójcikowska^{1,2} # *, Samia Belaidi^{1,3#}, Victoria Mironova⁴, Sylvie Citerne⁵, Hlne S.
4 Robert^{1*}

5
6 ¹ Hormonal Crosstalk in Plant Development, Mendel Centre for Plant Genomics and Proteomics,
7 CEITEC MU - Central European Institute of Technology, Masaryk University, Brno, Czech
8 Republic

9 ² Institute of Biology, Biotechnology and Environmental Protection, Faculty of Natural Sciences,
10 University of Silesia in Katowice, Katowice, Poland

11 ³ Laboratory of Functional Genomics and Proteomics, National Centre for Biomolecular
12 Research, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, Brno, Czechia

13 ⁴ Department of Plant and Animal Biology, Radboud Institute for Biological and Environmental
14 Sciences (RIBES), Radboud University, The Netherlands

15 ⁵ Universit Paris-Saclay, INRAE, AgroParisTech, Institute Jean-Pierre Bourgin for Plant Sciences
16 (IJPB), 78000, Versailles, France.

17 # These authors contributed equally to this work.

18 * Authors to whom correspondence should be addressed (barbara.wojcikowska@us.edu.pl and
19 helene.robert.boisivon@ceitec.muni.cz).

20

21 **ORCID**

22 BW 0000-0003-0287-9859

23 SB 0009-0006-4574-4005

24 VM 0000-0003-3438-0147

25 SC 0000-0001-5026-095X

26 HSR 0000-0002-6610-836X

27

28 **Running title**

29 MP and MP11ir required for somatic embryogenesis

30 9 Main Figures

31 1 Supplementary Table and 6 Supplementary Figures

32 7,769 words

33 **Abstract**

34 Auxin is crucial for plant morphogenesis, including *in vivo* and *in vitro* embryo development.
35 Exogenous auxin application is necessary for inducing embryogenic responses in *in vitro* cultured
36 explants of *Arabidopsis* and other plants. Thus, components of auxin transport, signaling, and
37 metabolism are key to somatic embryogenesis. AUXIN RESPONSE FACTOR (ARF)
38 transcription factors bind to auxin response elements to control auxin-responsive gene expression
39 and are vital in somatic embryo regeneration. ARFs are often repressed by AUXIN/INDOLE-3-
40 ACETIC ACIDS (Aux/IAAs). MONOPTEROS (MP)/ARF5 is especially important in the
41 embryogenic transition, being highly expressed during somatic embryogenesis; its mutant cannot
42 develop somatic embryos. The *MP11ir* transcript, an alternatively spliced variant of *MP*,
43 produces a truncated protein missing the Phox and Bem1p (PB1) domain, crucial for ARF-
44 Aux/IAA dimerization. This renders the MP11ir isoform insensitive to Aux/IAA repression,
45 suggesting an auxin-independent regulation. High levels of *MP11ir* transcript are observed
46 during auxin- and trichostatin A-dependent induction of somatic embryogenesis. Both MP and
47 MP11ir are essential for embryo regeneration in the *mpS319* mutant. However, overexpression of
48 a truncated MP protein (Δ ARF5) lacking the PB1 domain inhibits somatic embryogenesis,
49 resulting in callus formation instead of somatic embryos. Overexpression of Δ ARF5, lack of MP
50 protein (*mp* mutant), and interference with MP action by the auxin-resistant BODENLOS (BDL)
51 protein affect the expression of the genes *TRYPTOPHAN AMINOTRANSFERASE OF*
52 *ARABIDOPSIS 1 (TAA1)*, *TAA1-RELATED 1 (TAR1)*, *YUCCA3 (YUC3)*, *YUC5* and *YUC8*,
53 which are involved in auxin biosynthesis. The partial complementation of *mpS319* by the
54 expression of *MP11ir* may be due to the restoration of the expression of *TAA1*, *TAR1*, *YUC3*,
55 *YUC5*, and *YUC8* to the levels observed in the wild-type genotype Col-0. The presence of MP
56 protein alone or in combination with MP11ir in *mpS319* restored the expression of all analyzed
57 genes compared to Col-0. Our results suggest that the analyzed auxin-related genes could be
58 potential targets of MP11ir and/or MP. Consequently, Δ ARF5 overexpression alters auxin
59 homeostasis and endogenous auxin levels, hindering embryogenic transition.

60

61 **Keywords:** Alternative splicing; *Arabidopsis thaliana*; Auxin; AUXIN RESPONSE FACTOR;
62 Auxin signalling; *In vitro* culture; Isoform; MONOPTEROS; MP11ir; Somatic embryogenesis;
63 Transcription factor

64 **Introduction**

65 Auxin plays a vital role in various aspects of plant development, including plant growth and
66 morphogenesis in response to environmental signals through its transport, metabolism, and
67 signaling (Caumon and Vernoux, 2023; Cohen and Strader, 2024; Liu et al., 2024). Recognized
68 as a key trigger of developmental changes, auxin is a critical inducer of somatic embryogenesis
69 (SE) in many plant species (Elhiti and Stasolla, 2022). SE is a unique plant-specific
70 developmental process that demonstrates the pluripotency of somatic cells and is widely
71 exploited for *in vitro* plant regeneration. This technique is used in biotechnology for mass
72 micropropagation of plants (Mehbub et al., 2022), plant biodiversity conservation (Ballesteros et
73 al., 2024), and the production of transgenic plants (Lee and Wang, 2023; McFarland and
74 Kaeppler, 2024; Yang et al., 2024). With the rising global population, decreased crop yields due
75 to climate change, and increasing environmental pollution, the importance of *in vitro* plant
76 propagation techniques is growing (Hasnain et al., 2022; Krasteva et al., 2021). Understanding
77 the molecular mechanisms of SE can enhance its efficiency and its optimization for recalcitrant
78 species (Chen et al., 2022). Exogenous auxin treatment of explants modifies chromatin
79 accessibility and the transcriptome of somatic cells (Wang et al., 2020; Wu et al., 2022). This
80 modulation affects many genes, including those encoding transcription factors (TFs), proteins
81 associated with hormone transport, metabolism, signaling, and stress response. The induction of
82 SE is also associated with the expression of the genes encoding the core components of the
83 nuclear auxin signaling pathway, such as AUXIN RESPONSE FACTORS (ARFs) and
84 AUXIN/INDOLE-3-ACETIC ACIDS (Aux/IAAs) (Quintana-Escobar et al., 2019). Thus, the
85 crosstalk between auxin and these transcriptional regulators is fundamental to the SE regulatory
86 network.

87 MONOPTEROS (MP), known as AUXIN RESPONSE FACTOR 5 (ARF5), is pivotal in nuclear
88 auxin signaling and has been identified in many plant species (Chandler, 2016). The function of
89 MP is well-characterized, thanks to a wide range of tools like allelic mutants, overexpressing and
90 reporter lines in *Arabidopsis thaliana*, allowing for comprehensive functional, genetic, and
91 microscopic analyses (Hardtke et al., 2004; Odat et al., 2014; Rademacher et al., 2011; Schlereth
92 et al., 2010; Wójcikowska et al., 2023; Wu et al., 2015). Knowledge of the MP action is being
93 transferred to commercially important species (Liu et al., 2018a; Xu et al., 2019; Yue et al.,
94 2020). MP is crucial for many aspects of *in vivo* plant development, including flower, ovule, and

95 pollen development (Cucinotta et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2018b; Wu et al., 2015), zygotic
96 embryogenesis (Möller et al., 2017), root and shoot meristem establishment (Cole et al., 2009;
97 Krogan et al., 2016; Schlereth et al., 2010), organ polarity maintenance (Bhatia et al., 2016), and
98 vascularization patterns (Mattsson et al., 2003; Przemeck et al., 1996). MP is also critical for *in*
99 *vitro* plant morphogenesis. *MP* is essential for an effective SE process because its expression is
100 stimulated during SE; it is active in regions (cotyledons and SAM) where somatic embryos
101 emerge; and, more importantly, explants of *mp* mutant cannot produce somatic embryos
102 (Wójcikowska and Gaj, 2017).

103 The MP protein has four distinct domains: a B3-type DNA binding domain (DBD), dimerization
104 domains (DD1, DD2), a middle region (MR) region, and a Phox and Bem1 (PB1) domain
105 (Guilfoyle, 2015). MP binds to the AuxRE *cis*-elements in the promoter of target genes. As a
106 transcription factor, MP primarily acts as a positive regulator of gene expression (Boer et al.,
107 2014; Freire-Rios et al., 2020). In Arabidopsis, MP binds as a dimer to AuxRE motifs organized
108 as inverted repeats (IR), direct repeats (DR), and everted repeats (ER). IR consists of two
109 AuxREs on opposite DNA strands facing each other, DR has two consecutive AuxREs on the
110 same DNA strand, and ER features two AuxREs on opposite directions and DNA strands. The
111 DD1 and DD2 domains flank the DBD, acting as a caliper for binding to IR motifs. For docking
112 on ER and DR motifs, the MP DBD dimer relies on the MR or PB1 domains (Cancé et al., 2022).
113 Additionally, AuxRE elements in the MP promoter indicate that its expression is regulated by
114 cellular auxin level (Lau et al., 2011).

115 Three scenarios outline MP action. First, at low auxin levels, MP interacts with
116 BODENLOS/INDOLE-3-ACETIC ACID 12 (BDL/IAA12) via PB1 domains, recruiting
117 TOPLESS/TOPLESS RELATED (TPL/TPR), transcriptional co-repressor proteins, and HDA19
118 histone deacetylase enzyme. HDA19 removes the acetyl group from the histone H3 and H4 tails,
119 condensing the chromatin and blocking the expression of auxin-responsive genes (Chandler,
120 2016). In the presence of auxin, BDL is recruited by the SCF^{TIR/AFBs} complex, ubiquitinated, and
121 degraded by the proteasome, releasing MP to form a complex with SWI/SNF chromatin
122 remodeling ATPases BRAHMA (BRM) and SPLAYED (SYD). It unlocks the chromatin to
123 provide histone acetyltransferases (HATs) and transcription factors access to the *cis*-elements of
124 MP-regulated promoters, thus regulating gene transcription (Wu et al., 2015). Second, above-
125 threshold auxin levels may potentially cause MP protein oligomerization with itself or other

126 ARFs, inhibiting the expression of auxin-responsive genes, as observed *in vitro* (Korasick et al.,
127 2014; Nanao et al., 2014) and *in vivo* for ARF19 (Powers et al., 2019). This scenario is plausible
128 as plants with *MP* constitutive overexpression (Hardtke et al., 2004) phenocopy *mp* mutants
129 (Przemeck et al., 1996). Third, the *MP11ir* isoform, produced by alternative splicing (AS) of the
130 *MP* transcript during ovule and root development, lacks the PB1 domain due to the retention of
131 intron 11, resulting in the translation of a truncated protein. This isoform is insensitive to
132 Aux/IAA repression and could function independently of auxin. Ectopic expression of *MP11ir*
133 partially complements *mp* mutant phenotypes during reproductive development, indicating that
134 some MP functions do not require interaction with Aux/IAA repressors. *MP11ir* activates target
135 genes in ovule and root regions with low and high auxin concentrations (Cucinotta et al., 2021;
136 Cavalleri et al., 2024).

137 To understand the role of *MP11ir* in the embryogenic transition, we analyzed its transcript level
138 in *Arabidopsis* explants cultured *in vitro* and treated with SE inducers: auxins 2,4-
139 dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D), 1-naphthaleneacetic acid (NAA), and indole-3-acetic acid
140 (IAA), and trichostatin A (TSA). High *MP11ir* transcript levels were associated with auxin- and
141 TSA-dependent SE inductions. *MP11ir* can partially rescue the *mp* phenotype, improving its
142 capacity for embryogenic transition. However, both MP and *MP11ir* are required to fully
143 complement the *mp* phenotype. Overexpression of the truncated MP protein (Δ ARF5) inhibits SE
144 and alters the expression of auxin biosynthetic genes of the indole-3-pyruvic acid (IPyA)
145 pathway: *TRYPTOPHAN AMINOTRANSFERASE OF ARABIDOPSIS 1* (*TAA1*), *TAA1-*
146 *RELATED 1* (*TAR1*), *YUCCA 3* (*YUC3*), *YUC5*, and *YUC8*. This modulation changes
147 endogenous auxin levels, negatively impacting embryogenic transition. We hypothesized that
148 *MP11ir* may directly control *TAA1*, *YUC3*, *YUC5*, and *YUC8*. These findings suggest that
149 *MP11ir* is involved in SE induction alongside the canonical MP, contributing to the regulation of
150 auxin biosynthesis and homeostasis during this process.

151

152 **Results**

153 **The presence of *MP11ir* transcript is specific for auxin-dependent embryogenic transition**

154 *MP11ir* was first detected in ovules, where it likely regulates target genes in cells with low auxin
155 concentrations (Cucinotta et al., 2021). Given the critical role of auxin signaling proteins in the
156 embryogenic transitions, we investigated whether *MP11ir* would be active during SE induced by

157 exogenously applied synthetic auxin 2,4-D. We hypothesized that if *MP11ir* regulates its target
158 genes in cells with low auxin concentrations, its presence would be minimal in cells undergoing
159 embryogenic reprogramming, as those cells accumulate exogenous 2,4-D and endogenous IAA
160 (Schulz and Segobye, 2016; Wójcikowska and Gaj, 2015). To test this, we analyzed *MP11ir*
161 transcript levels in various samples: 10-day-old seedlings, flowers, leaves, immature zygotic
162 embryos (IZEs), and IZE explants during auxin-dependent SE induction. *MP11ir* was not
163 detected in leaves but was present in other tissues, notably flowers, as previously observed (Fig.
164 S1) (Cucinotta et al., 2021). Quantitative analysis revealed that *MP11ir* was most abundant
165 during the auxin-dependent embryogenic transition, with 11-18 times higher expression than in
166 seedlings (Fig. 1A). It suggests that *MP11ir* may regulate target gene expression in both low
167 (Cucinotta et al., 2021) and high auxin concentrations (our results; Cavalleri et al., 2024),
168 indicating a role in auxin-independent transcription control during SE.

169
170 **The presence of the *MP11ir* transcript depends on the type and concentration of**
171 **exogenously applied auxin**

172 To investigate the correlation between *MP11ir* transcript levels and auxin presence, we treated
173 IZEs with various auxins, i.e., 2,4-D, NAA, and IAA, at increasing concentrations (0, 2.5, 5.0,
174 and 7.5 μM) for ten days. Different auxins at the same concentrations had varied effects on
175 *MP11ir* levels. We observed a positive correlation between *MP11ir* levels and increasing
176 concentrations of 2,4-D (Spearman correlation coefficient 0.87; $p < 0.01$), NAA (Spearman
177 correlation coefficient 0.92; $p < 0.01$), but not IAA (Fig. 1 B-D). The application of 2,4-D had the
178 most substantial promoting effect on *MP11ir* levels. A 2.5 μM concentration of 2,4-D increased
179 *MP11ir* transcript levels 10-fold compared to untreated explants, while a 7.5 μM concentration of
180 2,4-D (three times higher) resulted in an 18-fold increase (Fig. 1B, E-H). The highest
181 concentration of NAA (7.5 μM) only increased *MP11ir* levels sevenfold (Fig. 1C, I-L). IAA did
182 not significantly affect *MP11ir* transcript levels (Fig. 1D, M-P). The strength of SE induction also
183 varied with the type of applied auxins (Fig. S2). In Arabidopsis IZE culture, 2,4-D is the most
184 effective for SE induction (Fig. S2A, D-G), followed by NAA (Fig. S2B, H-K), with IAA being
185 the least effective (Fig. S2C, L-O). We found a positive correlation between the increase of
186 *MP11ir* transcript levels and the strength of SE induction for 2,4-D (Spearman correlation
187 coefficient 0.80; $p < 0,01$) and NAA (Spearman correlation coefficient 0.75; $p < 0,01$) but not for

188 IAA. This data suggests that the type and concentration of auxin influence *MP11ir* levels and
189 subsequently affect the efficiency of the SE process.

190 **The presence of *MP11ir* transcript is specific for the embryogenic transition independently** 191 **of the presence of auxin**

192 Synthetic auxin 2,4-D is the most common and effective inducer of SE in Arabidopsis and other
193 plants (Wójcik et al., 2020). To determine whether *MP11ir* is specific for embryogenic transition
194 rather than merely responding to the application of exogenous auxins, which may also act as
195 stressors (Karami et al., 2023), we assessed the impact of trichostatin A (TSA), an inhibitor of
196 histone deacetylases (HDAC) known to induce SE (Tanaka et al., 2008), on the levels of *MP11ir*
197 transcript. IZE explants treated with 1 μ M TSA rapidly and massively regenerate somatic
198 embryos (Wójcikowska et al., 2018). We measured *MP11ir* levels on the 5th and 10th days of
199 TSA-dependent SE induction and found significantly elevated levels of *MP11ir*, 55 and 84 times
200 higher than in seedlings, respectively (Fig. 1Q). These findings suggest that *MP11ir* is
201 specifically associated with the developmental switch from somatic to embryonic cell fate,
202 highlighting its role in the embryonic transition (Fig. 1R).

203

204 **The *MP* transcript is detected during the SE process**

205 The transcript encoding the canonical MP protein was also detected during the SE process, which
206 is consistent with current knowledge (Wójcikowska and Gaj, 2017). Its expression pattern was
207 very similar to that of *MP11ir*. The *MP* transcript significantly accumulated in 2,4-D and NAA-
208 treated IZE explants (all concentrations tested) and in explants treated with 5.0 μ M IAA (Fig. 1S-
209 U). We observed a significant up-regulation of *MP* expression during auxin-dependent (Fig. 1V)
210 and TSA-dependent (Fig. 1W) induction of the SE process. During auxin- and TSA-induced SE,
211 *MP* is predominantly synthesized over *MP11ir* (Fig. 1X, Y). During the auxin-induced
212 embryogenic transition, the transcript level of *MP* was more than 100-fold higher than that of
213 *MP11ir*, whereas it was nearly 18-fold higher during TSA-induced SE (Fig. 1X). These results
214 indicate that both *MP* (Fig. 1Z) and *MP11ir* (Fig. S1B) transcripts are synthesized during somatic
215 embryogenesis, denoting their involvement in the embryogenic transition.

216

217 **Both *MP* and *MP11ir* are necessary to fully rescue the SE-related phenotypes of the** 218 ***mpS319* mutant**

219 Mutations in the *MP* gene dramatically reduce the capacity of IZE explants for SE. The *mpS319*
220 mutant showed impaired SE efficiency (20%) and productivity (2 somatic embryos per explant)
221 compared to Col-0 (85% efficiency and 4 embryos per explant) (Fig. 2A-D, H-J). Mutations in
222 *MP* affect zygotic embryo development, potentially impacting the capacity of the IZE to undergo
223 SE. To address this, we inhibited the MP-dependent signaling pathway by expressing an auxin-
224 insensitive BDL/IAA12 (*bdl*) protein in the IZE. Overexpression of DEX-induced *bdl* in IZE
225 completely abolished the embryogenic transition. Explants of the *p35S::bdl-GR* line treated with
226 DEX did not respond to the 2,4-D SE inducer and developed into seedlings. In contrast, Col-0
227 and the *p35S::BDL-GR* transgenic line expressing a native BDL protein that is ubiquitinated and
228 degraded by the proteasome in the presence of auxin, regenerated somatic embryos massively
229 and independently of the presence of DEX (Fig. 2N-X). These results confirm the findings
230 obtained with the *mpS319* line.

231 It was previously shown that *MP11ir* could partially rescue the *mpS319* mutant phenotypes
232 during ovule development (Cucinotta et al., 2021). To investigate the function of *MP11ir* and its
233 involvement in the SE process, we performed a complementation assay by expressing *MP11ir*
234 or/and *MP* under the control of the *MP* promoter (*pMP::MP11ir-GFP*, hereafter *pMP:MP11ir*
235 and *pMP::MP* transgenes) in the *mpS319* mutant. The presence of *MP11ir* improved the SE
236 capability of the *mpS319* mutant by 2.3-fold (Fig. 2A-B, E, K). Interestingly, canonical *MP* did
237 not fully rescue the *mpS319* SE defects, as only 48% of explants responded to SE induction in
238 *MP::MP mpS319* explants (Fig. 2A-B, F, L). Both *MP* and *MP11ir* transcripts must be present to
239 fully rescue the *mpS319* phenotype (Fig. 2A-B, G, M). The complementation assay showed that
240 *MP11ir* and *MP* are required together to fully rescue the *mpS319* SE defects and that both the
241 canonical and truncated *MP* proteins are necessary for effective somatic embryo formation.

242

243 **MP and MP11ir localization during the SE process**

244 To detect the *MP* and *MP11ir* protein during the auxin-dependent SE process, we used the
245 transgenic lines *pMP::MP-GFP* and *pMP::MP11ir-GFP*. The *MP* signal was detected at
246 different stages of SE induction (0, 1, 5, 10 days of culture) as a strong nuclear signal in the shoot
247 apical meristem, cotyledons, and root tip (Fig. 3A, C, E, G). Notably, the *MP* nuclear signal
248 progressively intensified and became widespread as the SE ages. In contrast, only faint and
249 diffuse fluorescence signal was detected for *MP11ir* at all stages of culture (Fig. 3 B, D, F, H).

250 The signal often lacks a clear nuclear localization pattern as observed for MP-GFP. This suggests
251 that MP11ir protein is either (i) expressed below detection levels, (ii) is not expressed in these
252 tissues under our experimental conditions, or (iii) subjected to post-transcriptional or -
253 translational modifications resulting in the absence of a clear nuclear GFP signal. Using available
254 lines, only MP protein was present during the SE process, suggesting that MP and MP11ir might
255 have distinct roles during the SE process.

256

257 **Overexpression of a truncated MP inhibits the SE process.**

258 To better understand the complex roles of full-length and truncated MP proteins in SE, we
259 examined the effects of ectopic expression of the truncated MP protein lacking the PB1 domain
260 (Δ ARF5), as MP11ir. We utilized a β -estradiol inducible *pXVE:: Δ ARF5 pDR5::GFP* transgenic
261 line to overexpress Δ ARF5. We observed that overexpression of Δ ARF5 inhibits the SE process
262 when explants are cultured on a 2,4-D supplemented medium (Fig. 4). Specifically, explants
263 overexpressing Δ ARF5 treated with 1 μ M β -estradiol and different concentrations of 2,4-D (1.0,
264 2.5, 5.0 μ M 2,4-D) developed callus tissue rather than somatic embryos. This finding underscores
265 that constitutive overexpression of Δ ARF5 affects morphogenesis and disrupts the transition to
266 embryonic development.

267

268 **Truncated and canonical MP proteins influence genes involved in auxin biosynthesis**

269 The inhibitory effect of Δ ARF5 overexpression on the SE process prompted us to investigate its
270 potential influence on endogenous auxin levels. SE inhibition often correlates with suboptimal
271 auxin concentrations during SE induction with IZE. Indeed, overexpression of the *LEAFY*
272 *COTELYDON 2 (LEC2)* gene, a master regulator of the embryogenic process during auxin-
273 dependent SE induction, resulted in SE inhibition due to increased endogenous auxin levels
274 (Wójcikowska and Gaj, 2015; Wójcikowska et al., 2013). Similarly, the combined treatment of
275 exogenous auxin and TSA inhibits SE in IZEs (Wójcikowska et al., 2018). To explore the link
276 between Δ ARF5-induced phenotypes and fluctuations in endogenous auxin levels, we examined
277 the expression of auxin biosynthetic genes from the IPyA pathway: *TAA1*, *TAR1*, *TAR2*, and the
278 flavin monooxygenases *YUC1-11*. These genes are expressed during the SE process and are
279 critical for auxin production during SE formation (Bai et al., 2013; Karami et al., 2023; Li et al.,
280 2022). Using the *pXVE:: Δ ARF5 pDR5::GFP* transgenic line, we induced Δ ARF5 overexpression

281 in explants cultured on 2,4-D supplemented medium with 1 μ M β -estradiol for 1, 5, and 10 days.
282 Our analysis revealed that Δ ARF5 overexpression significantly altered the expression of *TAA1*,
283 *TAR1*, *YUC3*, *YUC5*, and *YUC8* genes (Fig. 5A-C). Specifically, *TAA1*, *TAR1*, *YUC5*, and *YUC8*
284 showed increased expression levels after 24 hours of Δ ARF5 overexpression (Fig. 5A), whereas
285 *YUC3* and *YUC8* were upregulated on the 5th day (Fig. 5B). Ten days of overexpression of
286 Δ ARF5 maintained the up-regulation of *TAA1* and *YUC5* genes but resulted in the down-
287 regulation of *YUC3* (Fig. 5C). Further analysis in the *p35S::bdl-GR* line and the *mp* mutant
288 confirmed that *TAA1*, *TAR1*, *YUC3*, *YUC5* and *YUC8* are strongly down-regulated under
289 conditions of reduced MP function (Fig. 5D-F). The expression profiles of the other auxin
290 biosynthetic genes in *pXVE:: Δ ARF5 pDR5::GFP* (Fig. S3), *p35S::bdl-GR*, and *mp* lines (data not
291 presented) were mainly characterized by constant or reduced expression. To understand the
292 biological significance of MP11ir and MP in the *in vivo* regulation of *TAA1*, *TAR1*, *YUC3*, *YUC5*,
293 and *YUC8* genes, their expression was additionally analyzed in 5- and 10-day-old explants of
294 *pMP::MP11ir*, *pMP::MP*, and *pMP::MP11ir pMP::MP* lines in the *mps319* background (Fig.
295 5G, H). In 5-day-old explants, the expression of all tested genes in the presence of single or
296 combined MP and MP11ir proteins was similar to that in Col-0. In the 10-day-old explants, the
297 expression of *TAA1*, *YUC3*, and *YUC5* returned to the level observed in the wild-type genotype
298 Col-0 in the presence of MP11ir, in contrast to *TAR1* and *YUC8*, which remained lower than in
299 Col-0. In the presence of MP alone and in combination with MP11ir, the analyzed genes had the
300 same (*TAA1*, *YUC8*) or slightly higher (*YUC3*, *YUC5*) expression than in Col-0 and, notably, all
301 genes were characterized by a significantly higher expression than in the *arf5* mutant.
302 Interestingly, a synergistic effect of the MP11ir and MP on the expression of *YUC3* and *YUC8*
303 was significant compared to their individual effect.

304 Notably, a DAP-seq analysis (O'Malley et al., 2016) identified binding peaks for MP on the
305 promoters of *TAA1*, *TAR1*, and *YUC5* and for ARF2 on the *YUC8* promoter (Fig. S4). All the
306 genes deregulated in response to Δ ARF5 have at least one ARF-binding peak. These results
307 collectively suggest that MP, Δ ARF5, and thus presumably MP11ir, may positively regulate the
308 expression of genes involved in auxin biosynthesis, specifically *TAA1*, *TAR1*, *YUC3*, *YUC5*, and
309 *YUC8* genes.

310

311 **The localization of TAA1, TAR1, YUC3, YUC5, and YUC8 enzymes during induction of**
312 **the SE process is regulated by MP and MP11ir**

313 To elucidate the spatial distribution of the enzymes involved in the IPyA-dependent auxin
314 biosynthesis during the embryogenic transition, we utilized translational reporter lines for TAA1,
315 TAR1, TAR2, and YUCs proteins (Fig. S5). The TAA1, TAR1, YUC3, YUC5, and YUC8
316 enzymes were selected based on the RT-qPCR results (Fig. 5). To validate the regulation of their
317 expression by MP and $\Delta ARF5$, lacking the PB1 domain similar to MP11ir, we crossed the
318 translational reporter lines for TAA1, TAR1, YUC3, YUC5, and YUC8 into $pXVE::\Delta ARF5$
319 $pDR5::GFP$, $p35S::bdl-GR$, and mp lines to investigate any changes in the localization of GUS
320 signals. Explants were induced into SE with 2,4-D and 1 μM β -estradiol or 10 μM DEX to induce
321 $\Delta ARF5$ or bdl overexpression, respectively, and sampled on the 5th and 10th days of the culture.
322 Additionally, mp IZE (0 day) and explants on the 5th and 10th days of the SE process were
323 analyzed.

324 Among the enzymes analyzed, TAA1, YUC3, YUC5, and YUC8 exhibited distinct expression
325 patterns in response to $\Delta ARF5$ overexpression (Fig. 6). Notably, YUC8 showed robust
326 accumulation in the proximal regions of cotyledons and hypocotyl upon $\Delta ARF5$ overexpression,
327 as evidenced by intense GUS signals (Fig. 6A, Fig. 7E). Conversely, bdl overexpression led to a
328 significant decrease in GUS signal intensity for YUC8 (Fig. 6B, Fig. 7E). In mp mutant, the GUS
329 signal for YUC8 was absent (Fig. 6C, Fig. 7E), confirming the MP- and MP11ir-dependent
330 expression of the *YUC8* gene. TAA1 was broadly active throughout the IZE explants during
331 embryogenic transition (5th and 10th day), with a slight increase of the GUS signal upon $\Delta ARF5$
332 overexpression (Fig. 6A, Fig. 7A). However, changes in GUS intensity were modest upon bdl
333 overexpression or in mp mutant (Fig. 6B, C, Fig. 7A). YUC3 exhibits ubiquitous localization in
334 the hypocotyl region of explants, which is enhanced in the cotyledons upon $\Delta ARF5$
335 overexpression (Fig. 6A, Fig. 7C). In contrast, bdl overexpression deeply reduced the intensity of
336 the GUS signal (Fig. 6B, Fig. 7C), which was completely absent in mp mutant IZEs or reduced at
337 5th and 10th days of SE induction (Fig. 6C, Fig. 7C). YUC5 showed a specific accumulation at the
338 tip of the cotyledons only on the 10th day-old SE under $\Delta ARF5$ overexpression (Fig. 6A, Fig.
339 7D), with no changes observed during bdl overexpression (Fig. 6B, Fig. 7D). In mp mutant, the
340 GUS signal for YUC5 was restricted to single cells (Fig. 6C, Fig. 7D). In contrast, TAR1

341 localization was unchanged upon $\Delta ARF5$, and *bdl* overexpression, and in *mp* mutant (Fig. 6, Fig.
342 7B).

343 These findings demonstrated the cell-type-specific and temporal regulation of the TAA1, YUC3,
344 YUC5, and YUC8 auxin biosynthetic enzymes by $\Delta ARF5$, MP, and MP11ir proteins during the
345 SE process.

346

347 **Influence of MP11ir on endogenous auxin levels**

348 We hypothesized that MP11ir might regulate the endogenous auxin levels through TAA1, YUC3,
349 YUC5, and YUC8 during SE. We explored this hypothesis using three approaches. First, we
350 assessed local auxin responses in the *pXVE:: $\Delta ARF5$ pDR5::GFP* explants during the auxin-
351 independent embryogenic transition (1st and 5th days of TSA treatment) to avoid activation of the
352 *DR5* signal by the exogenously applied auxin. Explants were cultured on an ET medium with or
353 without β -estradiol. GFP signals indicate auxin-responsive gene transcription in the root and
354 shoot apical meristems and the tip of cotyledons in non-induced explants (Fig. 8A). After 24
355 hours of induced $\Delta ARF5$ overexpression, an enhanced GFP signal was observed in the hypocotyl
356 and throughout the cotyledons (Fig. 8B, E). In 5-day-old explants, $\Delta ARF5$ overexpression
357 intensified the GFP signal in the hypocotyl and cotyledons (Fig. 8C, D, F). Second, we quantified
358 indolic compounds and IAA in 21- or 10-day-old *in vitro* cultures, respectively, of *pXVE:: $\Delta ARF5$*
359 *pDR5::GFP* explants treated and not with β -estradiol (Fig. 8G, H). The explants overexpressing
360 $\Delta ARF5$, exhibiting callus formation, showed a 1.37-fold increase in indolic compound levels and
361 a 3-fold increase in IAA content compared to non-induced explants. Finally, to determine
362 whether the formation of calli might result from high auxin responses and indolic compound
363 levels, we analyzed the SE process in Col-0 and the *pXVE:: $\Delta ARF5$ pDR5::GFP* line treated with
364 different concentrations of yucasin (100 and 150 μ M), an inhibitor of YUC activity (Tsugafune et
365 al., 2017). (Non-)induced Col-0 (-E, +E) and non-induced *pXVE:: $\Delta ARF5$ pDR5::GFP* (-E)
366 explants treated with yucasin showed highly reduced SE efficiency (1.3 to 1.5 times lower) and
367 productivity (no more than two somatic embryos per reacting explant were formed) (Fig. S6).
368 The results align with published literature (Karami et al., 2023; Li et al., 2022). We then
369 investigated whether treating *pXVE:: $\Delta ARF5$ pDR5::GFP* IZE explants with yucasin could
370 reverse the phenotype induced by $\Delta ARF5$ overexpression with β -estradiol and enable the explants
371 to regenerate embryos instead of callus tissue. Indeed, these *pXVE:: $\Delta ARF5$ pDR5::GFP* IZE

372 explants formed a few somatic embryos (15.4% with 100 and 3.4% with 150 μ M yucasin) and
373 with low productivity (1 somatic embryo per reacting explant) instead of the calli observed in the
374 absence of yucasin (Fig. S6).

375 This finding supports that $\Delta ARF5$ overexpression amplifies local auxin responses by modulating
376 auxin production and signaling during SE, ultimately forming calli instead of embryonic
377 structures. However, other genetic components deregulated by $\Delta ARF5$ overexpression also likely
378 inhibit SE capacity.

379

380 **Discussion**

381 *MP* is upregulated in plant embryogenic cells and serves as a potential molecular marker for this
382 developmental stage. Various transcriptomic studies support the involvement of *MP* in the SE
383 process in various plant species (Awada et al., 2023; Capote et al., 2019; Chen et al., 2020;
384 Gliwicka et al., 2013; Indoliya et al., 2016; Juárez-González et al., 2019; Qi et al., 2021;
385 Quintana-Escobar et al., 2019; Shi et al., 2016; Thibaud-Nissen et al., 2003; Wickramasuriya and
386 Dunwell, 2015; Xu et al., 2024; Zeng et al., 2024; Zhu et al., 2023, Ge et al., 2025). Additionally,
387 the presence of *MP* transcripts in regions critical for SE induction, such as cotyledons and SAM,
388 suggests that *MP* may be involved in the embryogenic transition (Wójcikowska and Gaj, 2017).
389 Two *mp* mutant alleles, *arf5* (SALK_001058C) (Wójcikowska and Gaj, 2017) and *mpS319*
390 (SALK_021319) (present work), exhibit impaired SE processes. This inhibition is linked to the
391 differential expression of SE master regulators (Wójcikowska and Gaj, 2017). Similarly, the
392 *Osarf5* mutant displays partial defects in forming a scutellum-derived embryogenic callus. The
393 *Osarf5* mutant also shows a significantly reduced expression of *LEAFY COTELYDON 1*
394 (*OsLECI*), indicating that the OsARF5-mediated auxin signaling pathway might regulate
395 *OsLECI* (Guo et al., 2023a).

396 Expressing auxin-insensitive bdl protein during SE induction revealed that SE inhibition in the
397 *mp* mutant is not due to its embryonic defects but is triggered by *MP* inactivity in IZE. Many
398 *EMBRYO-DEFECTIVE* (*EMB*) genes involved in zygotic embryo development and
399 morphogenesis, such as *LECI*, *LEC2*, *FUSCA 3*, *DICER-LIKE 1*, *WUSCHEL RELATED*
400 *HOMEBOX 5* (*WOX5*), and *PIN-FORMED 1* (*PINI*), are also critical for SE processes
401 (Ledwoń and Gaj, 2009; Ledwoń and Gaj, 2011; Meinke, 2020; Su et al., 2015; Su et al., 2009;
402 Szyrajew et al., 2017). However, the overexpression of the auxin-insensitive bdl protein had a

403 more substantial impact on inhibiting embryogenic transition than the *mp* mutation, suggesting
404 that mutated *bdl* protein might repress other ARFs besides MP (Piya et al., 2014).
405 MP's transcriptional targets likely include genes encoding proteins essential to the SE process.
406 AGAMOUS-LIKE 15 (*AGL15*) and *AGL18*, crucial for SE (Harding et al., 2003; Paul et al.,
407 2022; Thakare et al., 2008; Zheng and Perry, 2014), might regulate *MP* expression as the *agl15*
408 *agl18* double mutant shows a significant reduction of *MP* mRNA levels (Zheng et al. 2009).
409 Also, inhibition of PHYTOCHROME-INTERACTING FACTOR 4 (*PIF4*) induces several auxin
410 responses (*ARF5*, *ARF8*, and *ARF16*) and biosynthetic (*YUC1*, *YUC2*, *YUC6*, *CYP79B2*, and
411 *AMIDASE 1 (AMI1)*) genes, resulting in the formation of the somatic embryos (Mira et al., 2023).
412 Despite these insights, the detailed mechanism of action of MP and its MP11ir isoform during SE
413 induction and somatic embryo formation remains unknown. Lines expressing truncated MP
414 proteins without the PB1 domain could elucidate the complex action of MP11ir by mimicking its
415 function. Truncated Δ ARF5 and MP^{abn} proteins partially rescue *mp* phenotypic defects but cause
416 unique leaf defects (Garrett et al., 2012; Krogan et al., 2012). Ectopic Δ ARF5 protein stimulates
417 the formation of new shoots *in vivo* (Ma et al., 2019), whereas *mpS319* mutants show reduced
418 shoot regeneration frequency (Zhang et al., 2021). During *in vitro* culture, Δ ARF5 increases the
419 shoot organogenesis frequencies in Arabidopsis root-derived explants and activates auxin
420 signaling. Visualization and cytometric quantification of the *pDR5::GFP* nuclear auxin signaling
421 reporter revealed an increased GFP signal in roots and protoplasts overexpressing Δ ARF5
422 (Gonzalez et al., 2021). A similar trend was observed after inducing Δ ARF5 expression during
423 the embryogenic transition. MP is involved in shoot apical meristem (SAM) activity and
424 maintenance by directly controlling the expression of ARABIDOPSIS HISTIDINE
425 PHOSPHOTRANSFER PROTEIN 6 (*AHP6*) (Besnard et al., 2014), TARGET OF
426 MONOPTEROS (TMOs) (Schlereth et al., 2010), DORNRÖSCHEN/ENHANCER OF SHOOT
427 REGENERATION 1 (*DRN/ESR1*) (Cole et al., 2009), *WUSCHEL RELATED HOMEBOXs*
428 (*WOXs*) (Lee et al., 2022; Tvorogova et al., 2019), essential for shoot regeneration or SE
429 (Fambrini et al., 2022). The shoot regeneration-promoting effect of Δ ARF5 (Ckurshumova and
430 Berleth, 2015; Gonzalez et al., 2021) may help to overcome organogenic resistance in recalcitrant
431 explants and species in the future. However, Δ ARF5 overexpression did not enhance
432 embryogenic capacity (our results) but instead led to callus formation, similar to *NcARF5*

433 overexpression in *Neolamarckia cadamba*, which triggers rapid callus proliferation (Ma et al.,
434 2024).

435 Studies on embryo-derived SE systems showed that SEs initiate from the callus edge, where
436 auxin accumulates, as visualized using PIN1 and DR5 reporters (Kadokura et al., 2018; Su et al.,
437 2015; Su et al., 2009). MP directly and positively regulates PIN1, which is responsible for auxin
438 efflux in polar auxin transport (PAT) (Krogan et al., 2016). Auxin is present in the *pin1* mutant
439 meristem, ensured by vascular tissue transport or induction of auxin biosynthesis (Banasiak et al.,
440 2019). Therefore, MP is proposed as a primary regulator of auxin transport and biosynthesis. Our
441 study identifies auxin biosynthetic genes, *TAA1*, *TAR1*, *YUC3*, *YUC5*, and *YUC8*, as potentially
442 positively regulated by Δ ARF5, MP11ir, and/or MP during *in vitro* embryogenic transition. We
443 propose that MP and MP11ir proteins directly or indirectly control the TAA1/TARs-YUCs-
444 mediated auxin biosynthetic pathway (our work) and polar auxin transport during embryogenesis
445 (Robert et al., 2015; Schlereth et al., 2010). This hypothesis aligns with findings that MP affects
446 *YUC1* and *YUC8* expression to specify the ground tissue in early globular zygotic embryos
447 (Möller et al., 2017). IPyA-dependent auxin biosynthesis is crucial for effective SE induction and
448 somatic embryo identity and growth (Li et al., 2022). Yucasin treatment, inhibiting YUC activity
449 (Tsugafune et al., 2017), reduces SE efficiency and productivity in Arabidopsis (Karami et al.,
450 2023; Li et al., 2022) and coffee culture (Uc-Chuc et al., 2020). The importance of auxin
451 biosynthesis in the SE process is evidenced by the decreased embryogenic response in *yuc*
452 mutants. Multiple *yuc* mutants, *yuc3 yuc8* (Li et al., 2022), *yuc1 yuc4 yuc10 yuc11* (Bai et al.,
453 2013), *yuc3 yuc5 yuc7 yuc8 yuc9* (Sakamoto et al., 2022), display disrupted SE or callus
454 formation compared to single mutants (Sakamoto et al., 2022; Wójcikowska et al., 2013). *YUC*
455 genes are direct targets of TFs, such as LEC1, LEC2, BABY BOOM (BBM), and AT-HOOK
456 MOTIF CONTAINING NUCLEAR LOCALIZED 15 (AHL15), which play pivotal roles in
457 embryogenic transition, demonstrated by decreased SE in their mutant and spontaneous induction
458 of somatic embryo formation when overexpressed (Boutilier et al., 2002; Gaj et al., 2005; Karami
459 et al., 2021; Ledwoń and Gaj, 2009; Lotan et al., 1998; Stone et al., 2001). During SE induction,
460 LEC1 activates *YUC4* and *YUC10* (Hu et al., 2018; Junker et al., 2012), while LEC2 positively
461 regulates *YUC1*, *YUC4*, and *YUC10* expression (Stone et al., 2008; Wójcikowska et al., 2013).
462 BBM induces local and ectopic expression of *YUC3* and *YUC8* coupled with IAA biosynthesis
463 and activation of the *WOX2* embryo marker (Li et al., 2022). During SE induction, AHL15

464 activates *YUC6*, *YUC7*, *YUC8*, and *YUC9* expression (Karami et al., 2023), confirming YUCs as
465 crucial molecular elements of a network governing the SE process.

466 We showed that both *MP11ir* and *MP* transcript levels increase along with the concentration of
467 auxins (2,4-D, NAA, IAA). The auxins analyzed in our study exhibited different potencies in
468 inducing SE, and with increasing auxin concentrations, a greater ability to induce SE was
469 observed. Similarly, the synthetic auxin 2,4-D was effective in SE induction, whereas natural
470 auxins were less efficient or even failed to induce regeneration (Karami et al., 2024). Why do
471 auxins act differently? 2,4-D cannot be efficiently transported and accumulates in the cells,
472 triggering a strong (optimal for SE) auxin response. In contrast, natural auxins are subject to polar
473 transport, which prevents their local accumulation and results in a moderate auxin response -
474 insufficient for SE induction. It has been shown that both natural auxins and synthetic analogs
475 become efficient inducers of SE when their efflux is transiently inhibited by an auxin transport
476 inhibitor. Explants of auxin efflux mutants, such as *pin2* and *abcb1 abcb19*, show enhanced SE
477 efficiency when treated with IAA or efflux-inhibited IAA, confirming that auxin efflux reduces
478 the efficiency of SE in Arabidopsis. Efflux-inhibited IAA, similar to 2,4-D, also efficiently
479 induced SE from carrot suspension cells, and efflux-inhibited 4-Cl-IAA improved *de novo* shoot
480 regeneration in *Brassica napus* (Karami et al., 2024).

481 A study identified target genes of MP and truncated Δ ARF5 proteins in 3-day-old seedlings
482 (un)treated with auxin (Xie et al., 2022). This ChIP-seq analysis suggests that deleting the PB1
483 domain renders the protein auxin-insensitive and alters its binding profile. Among genes involved
484 in the IPyA auxin biosynthesis pathway, *YUC3* and *YUC5* promoters are recognized and bound
485 by Δ ARF5, while the *YUC6* promoter is targeted by Δ ARF5 and MP. Differences in the
486 preferential AuxRE motifs bound by Δ ARF5 and MP suggest that the PB1 domain may affect
487 homodimer formation and DNA binding, indicating that Δ ARF5 and MP may differ in their
488 molecular actions and thus impact plant development differently (Xie et al., 2022).

489 Similarly, recent transcriptomic data revealed that MP and *MP11ir* may regulate the expression
490 of different sets of genes during Arabidopsis root development and have specific and non-
491 redundant functions. Among DEGs, *TAR2* (1.6 and 1.7-fold) and *YUC9* (1.5- and 1.8-fold) can be
492 distinguished with an increased expression in *pMP::MP* or *pMP::MP11ir* roots, respectively,
493 relative to the wild type. Other genes involved in Trp (IAA precursor) (*IGPS*, *TRP1*, *TSA1*,
494 *TSBtype2*) and IAA biosynthesis or conjugation (*AMII*, *NITI-3*, *IAMT1*, *MES17*, *CYP79B3*) are

495 also deregulated in an MP or MP11ir-dependent manner in root cells (Cavalleri et al., 2024). It
496 suggests that MP and MP11ir may regulate the expression of genes involved in auxin metabolism
497 and modulate cell's responsiveness to auxin.

498 Surprisingly, the lack of a GFP signal in the *pMP::MP11ir-GFP* SE makes it impossible to
499 follow the isoform localization. This may be due to a weak GFP signal, below the detection
500 threshold, or to post-transcriptional or post-translational modifications of the MP11ir-GFP
501 proteins. The *pMP::MP:EGFP(MR)* line, in which the EGFP sequence is inserted into the MR
502 domain of MP, upstream of the differentially spliced 11th intron, was used to localize MP11ir in
503 root (Cavalleri et al., 2024). Such a line, together with the *pMP::MP:VENUS-2Ap-*
504 *mTURQUOISE*, may allow the localization of MP and MP11ir proteins during the SE process.

505 Transcriptomic data have shown that many splice isoforms formed due to alternative splicing
506 (AS) show cell-specific expression (Klepikova et al., 2016; Martín et al., 2021). Among AS
507 events, intron retention events are functionally underestimated in plants. Given the importance of
508 AS in responding to various stresses, it is likely required for proper environmental response in
509 plants (Guo et al., 2023b). Limited functional evidence supports their specific expression patterns
510 or distinct ability to rescue mutant loss-of-function phenotypes. For example, *ARF8* undergoes
511 tissue-specific AS in flower, where the *ARF8.4* variant, which retains the eighth intron and has a
512 premature stop codon, is over-represented. Overexpression of *ARF8.4*, but not other *ARF8*
513 isoforms, reverts stamen elongation defects associated with the *arf8* knockout mutation (Ghelli et
514 al., 2023; Ghelli et al., 2018). Another example is the *BIGPETAL (BPE)* gene, which encodes a
515 petal-specific *BPEp* transcript that retains its last intron, in addition to the canonical *BPEub*
516 transcript uniformly expressed in all organs (Szécsi et al., 2006). The C-terminal sequence
517 exclusively encoded by *BPEp* is required to interact with ARF8. The *arf8* loss-of-function mutant
518 phenocopies the petal defects of the *bpe* knockout mutants, suggesting that BPEp, unlike the
519 canonical BPEub protein, is required for petal development (Kashkan et al., 2022; Varaud et al.,
520 2011).

521 In conclusion, both MP proteins, canonical MP and MP11ir isoform, seem to be involved in the
522 SE process (Fig. 9A). Potentially different expression patterns of MP and MP11ir suggest that
523 they act in different cells, probably with different endogenous auxin levels. The ectopic
524 expression of Δ *ARF5*, results in a global increase in endogenous auxin content in explants
525 through direct or indirect activation of *TAA1*, *TARI*, *YUC3*, *YUC5*, and *YUC8* genes. Disruption

526 of auxin homeostasis in explant cells by overproduction of TAA1, YUC3, YUC5, and YUC8
527 enzymes leads to SE inhibition and callus formation (Fig. 9B). Blocking MP action by expressing
528 the *bdl* repressor results in decreased levels of TAA1, YUC3, YUC5 and YUC8 enzymes during
529 SE induction, inhibiting the SE process and promoting seedling development (Fig. 9C). The
530 absence of both MP and MP11ir in *mp* mutant leads to the decreased TAA1 level, absence of
531 *YUC3*, *YUC5*, and *YUC8* during early stage of SE induction, resulting in SE inhibition and callus
532 formation (Fig. 9D). However, the analysis of auxin biosynthetic gene expression in the
533 complemented lines, expressing MP (*pMP::MP mpS319*), MP11ir (*pMP::MP11ir mpS319*) or
534 both proteins together (*pMP::MP pMP::MP11ir mpS319*), suggest that MP and MP11ir may
535 have common and specific transcriptional targets during SE, with MP11ir regulating *TAA1*,
536 *YUC3*, and *YUC5*, MP regulating *YUC8* and a synergistic MP and MP11ir effect on *YUC3* and
537 *YUC5*. In conclusion, by suggesting that MP and MP11ir are central regulators of auxin
538 biosynthesis during embryogenic processes, this study provides an elegant and straightforward
539 experimental setup that elucidates the role of MP and MP11ir in SE induction, acting through the
540 transcriptional control of auxin biosynthetic genes.

541

542 **Materials and methods**

543 **Plant material**

544 The seeds of *Arabidopsis thaliana* (L.) Heynh Columbia (Col-0) wild type, *mpS319* mutant
545 (N21319), reporter lines *pTAA1::TAA1-GUS* (N72246), *pTAR1::TAR1-GUS* (N72247),
546 *pTAR2::TAR2-GUS* (N72248), *pYUC1::YUC1-GUS* (N72250), *pYUC2::YUC2-GUS* (N72252),
547 *pYUC3::YUC3-GUS* (N72254), *pYUC4::YUC4-GUS* (N72256), *pYUC5::YUC5-GUS* (N72259),
548 *pYUC6::YUC6-GUS* (N72261), *pYUC7::YUC7-GUS* (N72262), *pYUC8::YUC8-GUS* (N72264),
549 *pYUC9::YUC9-GUS* (N72266), *pYUC01::YUC10-GUS* (N72268), and *pYUC11::YUC11-GUS*
550 (N72271) were supplied by NASC (The Nottingham Arabidopsis Stock Centre) (Alonso et al.,
551 2003; Brumos et al., 2019). Seeds of the *pMP::MP mpS319*, *pMP::MP11ir-GFP mpS319*, and
552 *pMP::MP11ir-GFP* transgenic lines were provided by Lucia Colombo (Dipartimento di
553 BioScienze, Università degli Studi di Milano, Milano, Italy). Dolf Weijers (Laboratory of
554 Biochemistry, Wageningen University, and Research, Wageningen, The Netherlands) generously
555 donated seeds of the *pMP::MP-GFP*, *p35S::BDL-GR*, *p35S::bdl-GR* lines. The seeds of the
556 *pXVE::ΔARF5 pDR5::GFP* line were provided by Bastiaan Bargmann (School of Plant and

557 Environmental Sciences, Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University, Blacksburg, USA).
558 The generation of *pMP::MP mpS319* x *pMP::MP11ir-GFP mpS319*, and *pXVE::ΔARF5*
559 *pDR5::GFP*; *p35S::bdl-GR*; *arf5* x *pTAA1::TAA1-GUS*, *pTARI::TARI-GUS*, *pYUC3::YUC3-*
560 *GUS*, *pYUC5::YUC5-GUS*, *pYUC8::YUC8-GUS* was performed by crossing.

561

562 **Plant growth and *in vitro* culture conditions**

563 Seeds were sterilized with sodium chloride (20% commercial bleach) and plated onto ½ MS
564 medium (Murashige and Skoog, 1962), (Duchefa Biochemie; #M0222), 10 g L⁻¹ sucrose (Penta #
565 57-50-1) and 8 g L⁻¹ agar (Duchefa Biochemie; #P1001). Seed-derived plants grown *in vitro* were
566 a source of seedlings, and *in vivo* were a source of leaves, flowers, and siliques for IZE isolation.
567 Plants were grown in soil with vermiculite (4:1) at 22 °C under a 16 h photoperiod of 100 μM m⁻²
568 s⁻¹ white, fluorescent light.

569

570 **Somatic embryogenesis induction**

571 IZEs at the cotyledonary stage of development were used as explants for the *in vitro* culture. The
572 IZEs were cultured on an E5 medium containing 3.2 g L⁻¹ of B5 micro and macro-elements
573 (Duchefa Biochemie; #G0210) (Gamborg et al., 1968), 20 g L⁻¹ sucrose, 5.0 μM of 2,4-D (2,4-
574 dichloro phenoxy acetic acid, Sigma-Aldrich #D7299) and 8 g L⁻¹ agar (Duchefa Biochemie;
575 #P1001), pH 5.8 (Gaj, 2001). To induce the SE process without auxin, the IZEs were cultured on
576 an ET medium containing 3.2 g L⁻¹ of B5 micro and macro-elements (Duchefa Biochemie;
577 #G0210) (Gamborg et al., 1968), 20 g L⁻¹ sucrose, 1 μM of TSA (Trichostatin A, Sigma Aldrich;
578 #T1952) and 8 g L⁻¹ agar (Duchefa Biochemie; #P1001), pH 5.8 (Wójcikowska et al., 2018).
579 Plant materials that grow in sterile conditions were kept at 23 °C under a 16 h photoperiod of 40
580 μM m⁻² s⁻¹ white, fluorescent light. The explant capacity for SE was evaluated in an IZE-derived
581 culture that was induced for 21 days on an induction media, and two parameters were calculated
582 – SE efficiency (percentage of explants that developed somatic embryos) and productivity
583 (average number of somatic embryos produced by embryogenic explant). Thirty explants were
584 analyzed in at least three biological replicates of the experimental combination. Around 10,000
585 IZEs were isolated for all the experiments. Assuming the average embryo isolation rate (100 IZEs
586 per hour), the time to obtain the research material for each experiment was 100 hours.

587

588 **IZE treatments**

589 IZEs at the cotyledonary stage were treated with different 2,4-D (Duchefa Biochemie; #D0911),
590 IAA (Duchefa Biochemie; #I0901) and NAA (Duchefa Biochemie; #N0903) (0.0, 2.5, 5.0, 7.5
591 μM) concentrations for ten days to evaluate the level of *MP* and *MP11ir* transcripts. IZEs were
592 cultured on a medium with 2,4-D and treated with different yucasin (Merck; #23711-26-4)
593 concentrations (0, 100, 150 μM) for 3 weeks to evaluate the effect of YUC activity inhibition on
594 the embryogenic capacity. Explants were first precultured for 1 day on a medium without yucasin
595 and transferred to a medium with different yucasin concentrations to allow for IZE survival.
596 Treating IZE explants with yucasin from the beginning of the culture (without preculture)
597 resulted in the death of the explants (Karami et al., 2023).

598

599 **Induction of *BDL*, *bdl*, and Δ *ARF5* expression in transgenic plants**

600 The action of *BDL* and *bdl* was controlled by adding dexamethasone (water-soluble DEX,
601 Sigma; #D2915) to the media at a concentration of 10 or 30 μM . The expression of Δ *ARF5* was
602 controlled by adding 1 μM β -estradiol (ethanol-soluble E, Sigma; # E8875) to the media.

603

604 **RNA isolation, reverse transcription, qualitative and quantitative PCR**

605 RNA was isolated from different samples, depending on culture age, tissue from 300 (0, 1st day),
606 150 (5th day) to 50 (10th day) explants were used for RNA extraction. A NucleoSpin RNA Plant
607 Kit (Macherey-Nagel) was used to isolate the RNA from the samples. The RNAs were treated
608 with RQ1 RNase-free DNase I (Promega) to control DNA contamination according to the
609 manufacturer's instructions. The first-strand cDNA was produced from 1,000 ng of RNA using a
610 RevertAid First Strand cDNA Synthesis Kit (Fermentas). The product of the reverse transcription
611 was used for RT-PCR and RT-qPCR reactions to detect and quantify gene transcripts. Undiluted
612 cDNA (1 μL) was used for RT-PCR. cDNA diluted with water at a 1:4 ratio (2.5 μL) was used
613 for the RT-qPCR reactions. RT-qPCR was carried out in a 10 μL reaction volume using a
614 LightCycler[®] 480 SYBR[™] Green I Master (Roche) kit, a LightCycler[®] 96 Multiwell Plate 96,
615 and MultiwellSealing Foil (Roche). The relative RNA levels were calculated and normalized to
616 the internal control of the AT4G27090 (*TIN*) gene encoding the 60S ribosomal protein (Thellin et
617 al., 1999). Fold change values were calculated using the comparative $2^{-\Delta\Delta C_t}$ method, where $\Delta\Delta C_t$
618 represents $\Delta C_t^{\text{reference condition}} - \Delta C_t^{\text{compared condition}}$. The $40-\Delta C_t$ method was used to compare the

619 expression levels of *MP* and *MP11ir* (Czechowski et al., 2004). The plant tissues for gene
620 expression analysis were produced in three biological replicates, and two technical replicates
621 were analyzed. Primer sequences for *MP11ir*, *MP*, *TIN*, *TAA1*, *TARs*, and *YUCCAs* are in Suppl.
622 Tab. S1.

623
624 **GUS staining**
625 The GUS enzyme activity was performed as described by Bassuner et al. (2007). The explants
626 were stained in a standard X-Gluc solution at 37 °C for 12 h. The experiments were repeated two
627 times for each studied combination, and at least 30 somatic embryos were subjected to GUS
628 signal detection in each repetition. The GUS staining pattern was analyzed using a microscope
629 Zeiss Axioscope.A1 ZEN.

630
631 **ClearSee alpha clearing and Renaissance SR2200 staining**
632 The explants were fixed using a fixative solution (4% paraformaldehyde in 1X PBS with 0.05%
633 Triton-X100 (PBS-T)) and incubated in a 1.5 mL fixative in a microcentrifuge tube for one hour
634 at room temperature. The tubes were covered with aluminum foil throughout the procedure to be
635 light-tight. The samples were vacuum infiltrated for ~30 min on ice to remove air bubbles.
636 Then, the samples were incubated overnight at 4 °C with slow rotation. The following day,
637 samples were washed three times with 1X PBS-T at room temperature for one hour each. A
638 ClearSee alpha solution was prepared according to Kurihara et al. (2021). The ClearSee solution
639 was supplemented with 50 mM sodium sulfite as an antioxidant. The clearing was extended to 7
640 days with gentle rotation (10-20 rpm) at room temperature to ensure thorough tissue penetration
641 and clearing. After clearing, a staining step was performed by mixing a 0.1% (v/v) Renaissance
642 SR2200 (Renaissance Chemicals, UK) solution in a ClearSee alpha solution (Attuluri et al.,
643 2022). After staining, the samples were washed in a fresh ClearSee alpha solution for one hour
644 and mounted on slides.

645
646 **Microscopy**
647 Expression pattern analysis was performed on a ZEISS AxioZoom.V16 microscope equipped
648 with an Apotome2 module, allowing for an overview of GFP signal localization. For higher
649 resolution and subcellular localization, particularly to assess nuclear localization of the GFP

650 signal, samples were subsequently examined using a ZEISS LSM 800 laser scanning confocal
651 microscope with a correction collar 10 \times magnification objective at 1024 \times 1024 pixel
652 resolution. Two laser lines were used: 405 nm for imaging Renaissance combined with 488 nm
653 for GFP imaging. The images were captured in 12 bits. The laser intensity and detector gain were
654 kept constant for all samples.

655

656 **Evaluation of indolic compound content**

657 A colorimetric technique that enabled the detection of indolic compounds, including IAA, was
658 applied (Bric et al., 1991; Wójcikowska et al., 2013). Each analysis was carried out in five
659 biological replicates.

660

661 **Evaluation of IAA content**

662 The concentration of indole-3-acetic acid (IAA) was evaluated in a 10-day-old IZE-culture of
663 *pXVE:: Δ ARF5 pDR5::GFP* transgenic line with 1 μ M β -estradiol-induced *Δ ARF5*
664 overexpression as described by Li-Marchetti et al. (2015). Fresh tissue was immediately frozen in
665 liquid nitrogen and stored at -80 °C. The samples were freeze-dried and ground. Approximately
666 3 mg of dry powder was extracted for each sample with 0.8 mL of acetone/water/acetic acid
667 (80/19/1 v:v:v). Indole-3-acetic acid stable labeled isotope used as internal standards were
668 prepared, as described by Le Roux et al. (2014). Analysis was performed on four biological
669 replicates.

670

671 **ARF binding regions**

672 We employed the DAP-Seq profiles for the MP and ARF2 transcription factors (O'Malley et al.,
673 2016) available at the PlantCistrome database (<http://neomorph.salk.edu/PlantCistromeDB>). We
674 analyzed (-1500; +100) *TAA1/TAR* and *YUC* gene promoters and detected TGTCnn sequences
675 and ARF-binding DAP-Seq peaks. We utilized a suite of R packages, including biomaRt, dplyr,
676 and ggplot2, for computational analysis and data visualization.

677

678 **Statistical analysis**

679 Phenotype scoring and quantification data were collected in EXCEL (Microsoft Corp.) and
680 imported into STATISTICA (TIBCO Software Inc., Palo Alto, CA, USA) for statistical analysis

681 and to generate graphs. For one-on-one comparisons, The Student's T-test was used ($p < 0.05$).
682 For intercomparison of more than two data points, the two-way ANOVA analysis ($p < 0.05$)
683 followed by Tukey's HSD test ($p < 0.05$, and $p < 0.01$) was used to determine any significant
684 differences between the compared combinations. The graphs show the means with the standard
685 deviations (SD).

686

687 **Data availability**

688 Raw images are provided in the Zenodo repository (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15357086)

689

690 **Supplementary Data**

691 Supplementary Figure S1. MP1 lir is expressed during somatic embryogenesis.

692 Supplementary Figure S2. The induction of somatic embryogenesis depends on 2,4-D and NAA,
693 not IAA.

694 Supplementary Figure S3. Expression level of auxin biosynthetic genes in *pXVE::ΔARF5*
695 *pDR5::GFP* somatic embryos.

696 Supplementary Figure S4. Analysis of the *TAA1*, *TAR1*, and *YUC* promoters of MP binding sites.

697 Supplementary Figure S5. Expression pattern of TAA1, TAR1, TAR2, and YUC1-11 during
698 somatic embryogenesis induction.

699 Supplementary Figure S6. Effects of repressing auxin biosynthesis in *pXVE::ΔARF5 pDR5::GFP*
700 during somatic embryogenesis induction.

701 Supplementary Table S1. The primers used in experiments.

702

703 **Funding**

704 B.W. was supported by the Polish National Agency for Academic Exchange
705 (BPN/BEK/2021/1/00278/U/00001). This work was supported by the project TowArds Next
706 GENERation Crops, reg. no. CZ.02.1.01/00/0.0/22_008/0004581 of the ERDF Programme
707 Johannes Amos Comenius from the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech
708 Republic. The IJPB benefits from the support of Saclay Plant Sciences-SPS (ANR-17-EUR-
709 0007). This research received funding from the National Science Centre, Poland, under the OPUS
710 call in the Weave programme (2023/51/I/NZ1/00704) and the Czech Science Foundation (25-
711 14425L).

712

713 **Acknowledgments**

714 We acknowledge the CEITEC core facilities Plant Sciences and CELLIM, supported by the
715 MEYS CR (LM2023050 Czech-BioImaging). This work has benefited from the support of IJPB's
716 Plant Observatory platforms P0-Chem. We are grateful to Lucia Colombo (Dipartimento di
717 BioScienze, Università degli Studi di Milano, Milano, Italy), Dolf Weijers (Laboratory of
718 Biochemistry, Wageningen University, and Research, Wageningen, The Netherlands), Bastiaan
719 Bargmann (School of Plant and Environmental Sciences, Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State
720 University, Blacksburg, USA) for providing seeds of Arabidopsis transgenic lines; Javier Brumos
721 Institute for Plant Molecular and Cell Biology (IBMCP), CSIC-Universitat Politècnica de
722 València, Spain, for consultation; Weronika Buchcik, Jagoda Polak, Wiktoria Remsak,
723 Agnieszka Kiwior-Wesołowska for technical assistance.

724

725 **Author contributions**

726 B.W. and H.R.B. designed and supervised the project. B.W., S.B., V.M., and S.C. conducted the
727 experiments and analyzed the data. B.W. and H.R.B. wrote the manuscript. All authors discussed
728 the results and approved the manuscript.

729

730 **Conflict of interest**

731 The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

732

733 **References**

734

735 Alonso, J.M., Stepanova, A.N., Leisse, T.J., Kim, C.J., Chen, H., Shinn, P., Stevenson, D.K.,
736 Zimmerman, J., Barajas, P., Cheuk, R., Gadrinab, C., Heller, C., Jeske, A., Koesema, E., Meyers,
737 C.C., Parker, H., Prednis, L., Ansari, Y., Choy, N., Deen, H., Geralt, M., Hazari, N., Hom, E.,
738 Karnes, M., Mulholland, C., Ndubaku, R., Schmidt, I., Guzman, P., Aguilar-Henonin, L.,
739 Schmid, M., Weigel, D., Carter, D.E., Marchand, T., Risseuw, E., Brogden, D., Zeko, A.,
740 Crosby, W.L., Berry, C.C., Ecker, J.R., 2003. Genome-wide insertional mutagenesis of
741 Arabidopsis thaliana. *Science* 301, 653-657.

- 742 Attuluri, V.P.S., Sánchez López, J.F., Maier, L., Paruch, K., Robert, H.S., 2022. Comparing the
743 efficiency of six clearing methods in developing seeds of *Arabidopsis thaliana*. *Plant Reprod* 35,
744 279-293.
- 745 Awada, R., Lepelley, M., Breton, D., Charpagne, A., Campa, C., Berry, V., Georget, F., Breitler,
746 J.C., L éran, S., Djerrab, D., Martinez-Seidel, F., Descombes, P., Crouzillat, D., Bertrand, B.,
747 Etienne, H., 2023. Global transcriptome profiling reveals differential regulatory, metabolic and
748 hormonal networks during somatic embryogenesis in *Coffea arabica*. *BMC Genomics* 24, 41.
- 749 Bai, B., Su, Y.H., Yuan, J., Zhang, X.S., 2013. Induction of somatic embryos in *Arabidopsis*
750 requires local YUCCA expression mediated by the down-regulation of ethylene biosynthesis.
751 *Mol Plant* 6, 1247-1260.
- 752 Ballesteros, D., Martínez, M.T., Sánchez-Romero, C., Montalbán, I.A., Sales, E., Moncaleán, P.,
753 Arrillaga, I., Corredoira, E., 2024. Current status of the cryopreservation of embryogenic material
754 of woody species. *Frontiers in Plant Science* 14, 1337152.
- 755 Banasiak, A., Biedroń, M., Dolzblasz, A., Berezowski, M.A., 2019. Ontogenetic Changes in
756 Auxin Biosynthesis and Distribution Determine the Organogenic Activity of the Shoot Apical
757 Meristem in *pin1* Mutants. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 20, 180.
- 758 Bassuner, B.M., Lam, R., Lukowitz, W., Yeung, E.C., 2007. Auxin and root initiation in somatic
759 embryos of *Arabidopsis*. *Plant Cell Rep* 26, 1-11.
- 760 Besnard, F., Refahi, Y., Morin, V., Marteaux, B., Brunoud, G., Chambrier, P., Rozier, F.,
761 Mirabet, V., Legrand, J., Lainé, S., 2014. Cytokinin signalling inhibitory fields provide
762 robustness to phyllotaxis. *Nature* 505, 417-421.
- 763 Bhatia, N., Bozorg, B., Larsson, A., Ohno, C., Jönsson, H., Heisler, M.G., 2016. Auxin Acts
764 through MONOPTEROS to Regulate Plant Cell Polarity and Pattern Phyllotaxis. *Curr Biol* 26,
765 3202-3208.
- 766 Boer, D.R., Freire-Rios, A., van den Berg, W.A., Saaki, T., Manfield, I.W., Kepinski, S., López-
767 Vidriero, I., Franco-Zorrilla, J.M., de Vries, S.C., Solano, R., Weijers, D., Coll, M., 2014.

- 768 Structural basis for DNA binding specificity by the auxin-dependent ARF transcription factors.
769 Cell 156, 577-589.
- 770 Boutilier, K., Offringa, R., Sharma, V.K., Kieft, H., Ouellet, T., Zhang, L., Hattori, J., Liu, C.M.,
771 van Lammeren, A.A., Miki, B.L., Custers, J.B., van Lookeren Campagne, M.M., 2002. Ectopic
772 expression of BABY BOOM triggers a conversion from vegetative to embryonic growth. Plant
773 Cell 14, 1737-1749.
- 774 Bric, J.M., Bostock, R.M., Silverstone, S.E., 1991. Rapid in situ assay for indoleacetic acid
775 production by bacteria immobilized on a nitrocellulose membrane. Applied and environmental
776 Microbiology 57, 535-538.
- 777 Brumos, J., Zhao, C., Gong, Y., Soriano, D., Patel, A.P., Perez-Amador, M.A., Stepanova, A.N.,
778 Alonso, J.M., 2019. An Improved Recombineering Toolset for Plants. The Plant Cell 32, 100-
779 122.
- 780 Cancé, C., Martin-Arevalillo, R., Boubekour, K., Dumas, R., 2022. Auxin response factors are
781 keys to the many auxin doors. New Phytol 235, 402-419.
- 782 Cavalleri, A., Astori, C., Truskina, J., Cucinotta, M., Farcot, E., Chrysanthou, E., Xu, X., Muino,
783 J.M., Kaufmann, K., Kater, M.M., Vernoux, T., Weijers, D., Bennett, M.J., Bhosale, R., Bishopp,
784 A., Colombo, L., 2024. Auxin-dependent post-translational regulation of MONOPTEROS in the
785 Arabidopsis root. Cell Reports 43(12).
- 786 Capote, T., Usié, A., Barbosa, P., Ramos, M., Morais-Cecílio, L., Gonçalves, S., 2019.
787 Transcriptome dynamics of cork oak (*Quercus suber*) somatic embryogenesis reveals active gene
788 players in transcription regulation and phytohormone homeostasis of embryo development. Tree
789 Genetics & Genomes 15, 52.
- 790 Caumon, H., Vernoux, T., 2023. A matter of time: auxin signaling dynamics and the regulation of
791 auxin responses during plant development. Journal of Experimental Botany 74, 3887-3902.
- 792 Chandler, J.W., 2016. Auxin response factors. Plant Cell Environ 39, 1014-1028.

- 793 Chen, Y., Xu, X., Liu, Z., Zhang, Z., XuHan, X., Lin, Y., Lai, Z., 2020. Global scale
794 transcriptome analysis reveals differentially expressed genes involve in early somatic
795 embryogenesis in *Dimocarpus longan* Lour. *BMC Genomics* 21, 4.
- 796 Chen, Z., Debernardi, J.M., Dubcovsky, J., Gallavotti, A., 2022. The combination of
797 morphogenic regulators *BABY BOOM* and *GRF-GIF* improves maize transformation efficiency.
798 *bioRxiv*, 2022.2009.2002.506370.
- 799 Ckurshumova, W., Berleth, T., 2015. Overcoming recalcitrance-Auxin response factor functions
800 in plant regeneration. *Plant signaling & behavior* 10, e993293.
- 801 Cohen, J.D., Strader, L.C., 2024. An auxin research odyssey: 1989–2023. *The Plant Cell* 36,
802 1410-1428.
- 803 Cole, M., Chandler, J., Weijers, D., Jacobs, B., Comelli, P., Werr, W., 2009. *DORNRÖSCHEN* is
804 a direct target of the auxin response factor *MONOPTEROS* in the *Arabidopsis* embryo.
805 *Development* 136, 1643-1651.
- 806 Cucinotta, M., Cavalleri, A., Guazzotti, A., Astori, C., Manrique, S., Bombarely, A., Oliveto, S.,
807 Biffo, S., Weijers, D., Kater, M.M., Colombo, L., 2021. Alternative Splicing Generates a
808 *MONOPTEROS* Isoform Required for Ovule Development. *Curr Biol* 31, 892-899.e893.
- 809 Czechowski, T., Bari, R.P., Stitt, M., Scheible, W.-R., Udvardi, M.K., 2004. Real-time RT-PCR
810 profiling of over 1400 *Arabidopsis* transcription factors: unprecedented sensitivity reveals novel
811 root- and shoot-specific genes. *The Plant Journal* 38, 366-379.
- 812 Elhiti, M., Stasolla, C., 2022. Transduction of Signals during Somatic Embryogenesis. *Plants*
813 (Basel) 11.
- 814 Fambrini, M., Usai, G., Pugliesi, C., 2022. Induction of Somatic Embryogenesis in Plants:
815 Different Players and Focus on *WUSCHEL* and *WUS-RELATED HOMEBOX (WOX)*
816 Transcription Factors. *Int J Mol Sci* 23.
- 817 Freire-Rios, A., Tanaka, K., Crespo, I., van der Wijk, E., Sizentsova, Y., Levitsky, V., Lindhoud,
818 S., Fontana, M., Hohlbein, J., Boer, D.R., Mironova, V., Weijers, D., 2020. Architecture of DNA

- 819 elements mediating ARF transcription factor binding and auxin-responsive gene expression in
820 Arabidopsis. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 117, 24557-24566.
- 821 Gaj, M.D., 2001. Direct somatic embryogenesis as a rapid and efficient system for in vitro
822 regeneration of Arabidopsis thaliana. *Plant Cell, Tissue and Organ Culture* 64, 39-46.
- 823 Gaj, M.D., Zhang, S., Harada, J.J., Lemaux, P.G., 2005. Leafy cotyledon genes are essential for
824 induction of somatic embryogenesis of Arabidopsis. *Planta* 222, 977-988.
- 825 Gamborg, O.L.c., Miller, R.A., Ojima, K., 1968. Nutrient requirements of suspension cultures of
826 soybean root cells. *Experimental cell research* 50, 151-158.
- 827 Garrett, J.J., Meents, M.J., Blackshaw, M.T., Blackshaw, L.C., Hou, H., Styranko, D.M.,
828 Kohalmi, S.E., Schultz, E.A., 2012. A novel, semi-dominant allele of MONOPTEROS provides
829 insight into leaf initiation and vein pattern formation. *Planta* 236, 297-312.
- 830 Ge, X., Yu, X., Liu, Z., Yuan, J., Qin, A., Wang, Y., Chen, Y., Qin, W., Liu, Y., Liu, X., Zhou,
831 Y., Wang, P., Yang, J., Liu, H., Zhao, Z., Hu, M., Zhang, Y., Sun, S., Herrera-Estrella, L.,
832 Phan Tran, L.S., Sun, X., Li, F., 2025. Spatiotemporal transcriptome and metabolome
833 landscapes of cotton somatic embryos. *Nature Communications*, 16, 859.
- 834 Ghelli, R., Brunetti, P., Marzi, D., Cecchetti, V., Costantini, M., Lanzoni-Rossi, M., Scaglia
835 Linhares, F., Costantino, P., Cardarelli, M., 2023. The full-length Auxin Response Factor 8
836 isoform ARF8.1 controls pollen cell wall formation and directly regulates TDF1, AMS and
837 MS188 expression. *Plant J* 113, 851-865.
- 838 Ghelli, R., Brunetti, P., Napoli, N., De Paolis, A., Cecchetti, V., Tsuge, T., Serino, G., Matsui,
839 M., Mele, G., Rinaldi, G., Palumbo, G.A., Barozzi, F., Costantino, P., Cardarelli, M., 2018. A
840 Newly Identified Flower-Specific Splice Variant of AUXIN RESPONSE FACTOR8 Regulates
841 Stamen Elongation and Endothecium Lignification in Arabidopsis. *Plant Cell* 30, 620-637.
- 842 Gliwicka, M., Nowak, K., Balazadeh, S., Mueller-Roeber, B., Gaj, M.D., 2013. Extensive
843 modulation of the transcription factor transcriptome during somatic embryogenesis in
844 Arabidopsis thaliana. *PLoS One* 8, e69261.

- 845 Gonzalez, J.H., Taylor, J.S., Reed, K.M., Wright, R.C., Bargmann, B.O., 2021. Temporal control
846 of morphogenic factor expression determines efficacy in enhancing regeneration. *Plants* 10, 2271.
- 847 Guilfoyle, T.J., 2015. The PB1 domain in auxin response factor and Aux/IAA proteins: a
848 versatile protein interaction module in the auxin response. *Plant Cell* 27, 33-43.
- 849 Guo, F., Wang, H., Lian, G., Cai, G., Liu, W., Zhang, H., Li, D., Zhou, C., Han, N., Zhu, M., Su,
850 Y., Seo, P.J., Xu, L., Bian, H., 2023a. Initiation of scutellum-derived callus is regulated by an
851 embryo-like developmental pathway in rice. *Communications Biology* 6, 457.
- 852 Guo, X., Wang, T., Jiang, L., Qi, H., Zhang, Z., 2023b. PlaASDB: a comprehensive database of
853 plant alternative splicing events in response to stress. *BMC plant biology* 23, 225.
- 854 Harding, E.W., Tang, W., Nichols, K.W., Fernandez, D.E., Perry, S.E., 2003. Expression and
855 maintenance of embryogenic potential is enhanced through constitutive expression of
856 AGAMOUS-Like 15. *Plant Physiol* 133, 653-663.
- 857 Hardtke, C.S., Ckurshumova, W., Vidaurre, D.P., Singh, S.A., Stamatiou, G., Tiwari, S.B.,
858 Hagen, G., Guilfoyle, T.J., Berleth, T., 2004. Overlapping and non-redundant functions of the
859 Arabidopsis auxin response factors MONOPTEROS and NONPHOTOTROPIC HYPOCOTYL
860 4. *Development* 131, 1089-1100.
- 861 Hasnain, A., Naqvi, S.A.H., Ayesha, S.I., Khalid, F., Ellahi, M., Iqbal, S., Hassan, M.Z., Abbas,
862 A., Adamski, R., Markowska, D., 2022. Plants in vitro propagation with its applications in food,
863 pharmaceuticals and cosmetic industries; current scenario and future approaches. *Frontiers in*
864 *plant science* 13, 1009395.
- 865 Hu, Y., Zhou, L., Huang, M., He, X., Yang, Y., Liu, X., Li, Y., Hou, X., 2018. Gibberellins play
866 an essential role in late embryogenesis of Arabidopsis. *Nature Plants* 4, 289-298.
- 867 Indoliya, Y., Tiwari, P., Chauhan, A.S., Goel, R., Shri, M., Bag, S.K., Chakrabarty, D., 2016.
868 Decoding regulatory landscape of somatic embryogenesis reveals differential regulatory networks
869 between japonica and indica rice subspecies. *Sci Rep* 6, 23050.

- 870 Juárez-González, V.T., López-Ruiz, B.A., Baldrich, P., Luján-Soto, E., Meyers, B.C., Dinkova,
871 T.D., 2019. The explant developmental stage profoundly impacts small RNA-mediated regulation
872 at the dedifferentiation step of maize somatic embryogenesis. *Sci Rep* 9, 14511.
- 873 Junker, A., Mönke, G., Rutten, T., Keilwagen, J., Seifert, M., Thi, T.M., Renou, J.P., Balzergue,
874 S., Viehöver, P., Hähnel, U., Ludwig-Müller, J., Altschmied, L., Conrad, U., Weisshaar, B.,
875 Bäumlein, H., 2012. Elongation-related functions of LEAFY COTYLEDON1 during the
876 development of *Arabidopsis thaliana*. *Plant J* 71, 427-442.
- 877 Kadokura, S., Sugimoto, K., Tarr, P., Suzuki, T., Matsunaga, S., 2018. Characterization of
878 somatic embryogenesis initiated from the *Arabidopsis* shoot apex. *Dev Biol* 442, 13-27.
- 879 Karami, O., de Jong, H., Somovilla, V.J., Villanueva Acosta, B., Sugiarta, A.B., Ham, M.,
880 Khadem, A., Wennekes, T., Offringa, R., 2023. Structure–activity relationship of 2,4-D correlates
881 auxinic activity with the induction of somatic embryogenesis in *Arabidopsis thaliana*. *Plant J* 116,
882 1355-1369.
- 883 Karami, O., Khadem, A., Rahimi, A., Zagari, N., Aigner, S. and Offringa, R., 2024. Transient
884 efflux inhibition improves plant regeneration by natural auxins. *Plant J* 118, 295-303.
- 885 Karami, O., Philipsen, C., Rahimi, A., Nurillah, A.R., Boutilier, K., Offringa, R., 2023.
886 Endogenous auxin maintains embryonic cell identity and promotes somatic embryo development
887 in *Arabidopsis*. *Plant J* 113, 7-22.
- 888 Karami, O., Rahimi, A., Mak, P., Horstman, A., Boutilier, K., Compier, M., van der Zaal, B.,
889 Offringa, R., 2021. An *Arabidopsis* AT-hook motif nuclear protein mediates somatic
890 embryogenesis and coinciding genome duplication. *Nat Commun* 12, 2508.
- 891 Kashkan, I., Timofeyenko, K., Růžička, K., 2022. How alternative splicing changes the
892 properties of plant proteins. *Quant Plant Biol* 3, e14.
- 893 Klepikova, A.V., Kasianov, A.S., Gerasimov, E.S., Logacheva, M.D., Penin, A.A., 2016. A high
894 resolution map of the *Arabidopsis thaliana* developmental transcriptome based on RNA-seq
895 profiling. *The Plant Journal* 88, 1058-1070.

- 896 Korasick, D.A., Westfall, C.S., Lee, S.G., Nanao, M.H., Dumas, R., Hagen, G., Guilfoyle, T.J.,
897 Jez, J.M., Strader, L.C., 2014. Molecular basis for AUXIN RESPONSE FACTOR protein
898 interaction and the control of auxin response repression. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 111, 5427-
899 5432.
- 900 Krasteva, G., Georgiev, V., Pavlov, A., 2021. Recent applications of plant cell culture technology
901 in cosmetics and foods. *Engineering in Life Sciences* 21, 68-76.
- 902 Krogan, N.T., Ckurshumova, W., Marcos, D., Caragea, A.E., Berleth, T., 2012. Deletion of
903 MP/ARF5 domains III and IV reveals a requirement for Aux/IAA regulation in Arabidopsis leaf
904 vascular patterning. *New Phytol* 194, 391-401.
- 905 Krogan, N.T., Marcos, D., Weiner, A.I., Berleth, T., 2016. The auxin response factor
906 MONOPTEROS controls meristem function and organogenesis in both the shoot and root
907 through the direct regulation of PIN genes. *New Phytol* 212, 42-50.
- 908 Kurihara, D., Mizuta, Y., Nagahara, S., Higashiyama, T., 2021. ClearSeeAlpha: advanced optical
909 clearing for whole-plant imaging. *Plant and Cell Physiology* 62, 1302-1310.
- 910 Lau, S., De Smet, I., Kolb, M., Meinhardt, H., Jürgens, G., 2011. Auxin triggers a genetic switch.
911 *Nat Cell Biol* 13, 611-615.
- 912 Le Roux, C., Del Prete, S., Boutet-Mercey, S., Perreau, F., Balague, C., Roby, D., Fagard, M.,
913 Gaudin, V. 2014. The hnRNP-Q protein LIF2 participates in the plant immune response. *PLoS*
914 *ONE* 9(6):e99343.
- 915 Ledwoń, A., Gaj, M.D., 2009. LEAFY COTYLEDON2 gene expression and auxin treatment in
916 relation to embryogenic capacity of Arabidopsis somatic cells. *Plant Cell Rep* 28, 1677-1688.
- 917 Ledwoń, A., Gaj, M.D., 2011. LEAFY COTYLEDON1, FUSCA3 expression and auxin
918 treatment in relation to somatic embryogenesis induction in Arabidopsis. *Plant Growth*
919 *Regulation* 65, 157-167.
- 920 Lee, K., Kim, J.H., Park, O.S., Jung, Y.J., Seo, P.J., 2022. Ectopic expression of WOX5 promotes
921 cytokinin signaling and de novo shoot regeneration. *Plant Cell Rep* 41, 2415-2422.

- 922 Lee, K., Wang, K., 2023. Strategies for genotype-flexible plant transformation. *Current Opinion*
923 *in Biotechnology* 79, 102848.
- 924 Li, M., Wrobel-Marek, J., Heidmann, I., Horstman, A., Chen, B., Reis, R., Angenent, G.C.,
925 Boutilier, K., 2022. Auxin biosynthesis maintains embryo identity and growth during BABY
926 BOOM-induced somatic embryogenesis. *Plant Physiol* 188, 1095-1110.
- 927 Li-Marchetti, C., Le Bras, C., Relion, D., Citerne, S., Huché-Thélier, L., Sakr, S., Morel, P.,
928 Crespel, L. 2015. Genotypic differences in architectural and physiological responses to water
929 restriction in rose bush. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 6, 355.
- 930 Liu, L., Yahaya, B.S., Li, J., Wu, F., 2024. Enigmatic role of auxin response factors in plant
931 growth and stress tolerance. *Frontiers in Plant Science* 15, 1398818.
- 932 Liu, S., Zhang, Y., Feng, Q., Qin, L., Pan, C., Lamin-Samu, A.T., Lu, G., 2018a. Tomato AUXIN
933 RESPONSE FACTOR 5 regulates fruit set and development via the mediation of auxin and
934 gibberellin signaling. *Sci Rep* 8, 2971.
- 935 Liu, Z., Miao, L., Huo, R., Song, X., Johnson, C., Kong, L., Sundaresan, V., Yu, X., 2018b.
936 ARF2–ARF4 and ARF5 are essential for female and male gametophyte development in
937 Arabidopsis. *Plant and Cell Physiology* 59, 179-189.
- 938 Lotan, T., Ohto, M.-a., Yee, K.M., West, M.A., Lo, R., Kwong, R.W., Yamagishi, K., Fischer,
939 R.L., Goldberg, R.B., Harada, J.J., 1998. Arabidopsis LEAFY COTYLEDON1 is sufficient to
940 induce embryo development in vegetative cells. *Cell* 93, 1195-1205.
- 941 Ma, Y., Miotk, A., Šutiković, Z., Ermakova, O., Wenzl, C., Medzihradzky, A., Gaillochet, C.,
942 Forner, J., Utan, G., Brackmann, K., Galván-Ampudia, C.S., Vernoux, T., Greb, T., Lohmann,
943 J.U., 2019. WUSCHEL acts as an auxin response rheostat to maintain apical stem cells in
944 Arabidopsis. *Nat Commun* 10, 5093.
- 945 Ma, Y., Zhao, B., Zhang, D., Ouyang, K., Li, J., 2024. Transcriptomic and functional analyses
946 identify genes associated with embryogenic callus formation in *Neolamarckia cadamba*.
947 *Industrial Crops and Products* 216, 118686.

- 948 Martín, G., Márquez, Y., Mantica, F., Duque, P., Irimia, M., 2021. Alternative splicing
949 landscapes in *Arabidopsis thaliana* across tissues and stress conditions highlight major functional
950 differences with animals. *Genome biology* 22, 1-26.
- 951 Mattsson, J., Ckurshumova, W., Berleth, T., 2003. Auxin signaling in *Arabidopsis* leaf vascular
952 development. *Plant Physiol* 131, 1327-1339.
- 953 McFarland, F.L., Kaeppler, H.F., 2024. History and current status of embryogenic culture-based
954 tissue culture, transformation and gene editing of maize (*Zea mays* L.). *The Plant Genome*,
955 e20451.
- 956 Mehbub, H., Akter, A., Akter, M.A., Mandal, M.S.H., Hoque, M.A., Tuleja, M., Mehraj, H.,
957 2022. Tissue Culture in Ornamentals: Cultivation Factors, Propagation Techniques, and Its
958 Application. *Plants (Basel)* 11.
- 959 Meinke, D.W., 2020. Genome-wide identification of EMBRYO-DEFECTIVE (EMB) genes
960 required for growth and development in *Arabidopsis*. *New Phytologist* 226, 306-325.
- 961 Mira, M.M., Day, S., Ibrahim, S., Hill, R.D., Stasolla, C., 2023. The *Arabidopsis* Phytochrome 2
962 mediates phytochrome B (phyB) light signaling responses during somatic embryogenesis. *Planta*
963 257, 88.
- 964 Möller, B.K., Ten Hove, C.A., Xiang, D., Williams, N., López, L.G., Yoshida, S., Smit, M.,
965 Datla, R., Weijers, D., 2017. Auxin response cell-autonomously controls ground tissue initiation
966 in the early *Arabidopsis* embryo. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 114, E2533-e2539.
- 967 Murashige, T., Skoog, F., 1962. A Revised Medium for Rapid Growth and Bio Assays with
968 Tobacco Tissue Cultures. *Physiologia Plantarum* 15, 473-497.
- 969 Nanao, M.H., Vinos-Poyo, T., Brunoud, G., Thévenon, E., Mazzoleni, M., Mast, D., Lainé, S.,
970 Wang, S., Hagen, G., Li, H., Guilfoyle, T.J., Parcy, F., Vernoux, T., Dumas, R., 2014. Structural
971 basis for oligomerization of auxin transcriptional regulators. *Nat Commun* 5, 3617.

- 972 O'Malley, R.C., Huang, S.C., Song, L., Lewsey, M.G., Bartlett, A., Nery, J.R., Galli, M.,
973 Gallavotti, A., Ecker, J.R., 2016. Cistrome and Epicistrome Features Shape the Regulatory DNA
974 Landscape. *Cell* 165, 1280-1292.
- 975 Odat, O., Gardiner, J., Sawchuk, M.G., Verna, C., Donner, T.J., Scarpella, E., 2014.
976 Characterization of an allelic series in the MONOPTEROS gene of Arabidopsis. *Genesis* 52, 127-
977 133.
- 978 Paul, P., Joshi, S., Tian, R., Diogo Junior, R., Chakrabarti, M., Perry, S.E., 2022. The MADS-
979 domain factor AGAMOUS-Like18 promotes somatic embryogenesis. *Plant Physiol* 188, 1617-
980 1631.
- 981 Piya, S., Shrestha, S.K., Binder, B., Stewart, C.N., Jr., Hewezi, T., 2014. Protein-protein
982 interaction and gene co-expression maps of ARFs and Aux/IAAs in Arabidopsis. *Front Plant Sci*
983 5, 744.
- 984 Powers, S.K., Holehouse, A.S., Korasick, D.A., Schreiber, K.H., Clark, N.M., Jing, H.,
985 Emenecker, R., Han, S., Tycksen, E., Hwang, I., Sozzani, R., Jez, J.M., Pappu, R.V., Strader,
986 L.C., 2019. Nucleo-cytoplasmic Partitioning of ARF Proteins Controls Auxin Responses in
987 Arabidopsis thaliana. *Mol Cell* 76, 177-190.e175.
- 988 Przemeck, G.K., Mattsson, J., Hardtke, C.S., Sung, Z.R., Berleth, T., 1996. Studies on the role of
989 the Arabidopsis gene MONOPTEROS in vascular development and plant cell axialization. *Planta*
990 200, 229-237.
- 991 Qi, S., Zhao, R., Yan, J., Fan, Y., Huang, C., Li, H., Chen, S., Zhang, T., Kong, L., Zhao, J.,
992 Zhang, J., 2021. Global Transcriptome and Coexpression Network Analyses Reveal New Insights
993 Into Somatic Embryogenesis in Hybrid Sweetgum (*Liquidambar styraciflua* × *Liquidambar*
994 *formosana*). *Front Plant Sci* 12, 751866.
- 995 Quintana-Escobar, A.O., Nic-Can, G.I., Galaz Avalos, R.M., Loyola-Vargas, V.M., Gongora-
996 Castillo, E., 2019. Transcriptome analysis of the induction of somatic embryogenesis in *Coffea*
997 *canephora* and the participation of ARF and Aux/IAA genes. *PeerJ* 7, e7752.

- 998 Rademacher, E.H., Möller, B., Lokerse, A.S., Llavata-Peris, C.I., van den Berg, W., Weijers, D.,
999 2011. A cellular expression map of the Arabidopsis AUXIN RESPONSE FACTOR gene family.
1000 *Plant J* 68, 597-606.
- 1001 Robert, H.S., Grunewald, W., Sauer, M., Cannoot, B., Soriano, M., Swarup, R., Weijers, D.,
1002 Bennett, M., Boutilier, K., Friml, J., 2015. Plant embryogenesis requires AUX/LAX-mediated
1003 auxin influx. *Development* 142, 702-711.
- 1004 Sakamoto, Y., Kawamura, A., Suzuki, T., Segami, S., Maeshima, M., Polyn, S., De Veylder, L.,
1005 Sugimoto, K., 2022. Transcriptional activation of auxin biosynthesis drives developmental
1006 reprogramming of differentiated cells. *Plant Cell* 34, 4348-4365.
- 1007 Schlereth, A., Möller, B., Liu, W., Kientz, M., Flipse, J., Rademacher, E.H., Schmid, M., Jürgens,
1008 G., Weijers, D., 2010. MONOPTEROS controls embryonic root initiation by regulating a mobile
1009 transcription factor. *Nature* 464, 913-916.
- 1010 Schulz, B., Segobye, K., 2016. 2, 4-D transport and herbicide resistance in weeds. *Journal of*
1011 *Experimental Botany* 67, 3177-3179.
- 1012 Shi, X., Zhang, C., Liu, Q., Zhang, Z., Zheng, B., Bao, M., 2016. De novo comparative
1013 transcriptome analysis provides new insights into sucrose induced somatic embryogenesis in
1014 camphor tree (*Cinnamomum camphora* L.). *BMC Genomics* 17, 26.
- 1015 Stone, S.L., Braybrook, S.A., Paula, S.L., Kwong, L.W., Meuser, J., Pelletier, J., Hsieh, T.F.,
1016 Fischer, R.L., Goldberg, R.B., Harada, J.J., 2008. Arabidopsis LEAFY COTYLEDON2 induces
1017 maturation traits and auxin activity: Implications for somatic embryogenesis. *Proc Natl Acad Sci*
1018 *U S A* 105, 3151-3156.
- 1019 Stone, S.L., Kwong, L.W., Yee, K.M., Pelletier, J., Lepiniec, L., Fischer, R.L., Goldberg, R.B.,
1020 Harada, J.J., 2001. LEAFY COTYLEDON2 encodes a B3 domain transcription factor that
1021 induces embryo development. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 98, 11806-11811.
- 1022 Su, Y.H., Liu, Y.B., Bai, B., Zhang, X.S., 2015. Establishment of embryonic shoot–root axis is
1023 involved in auxin and cytokinin response during Arabidopsis somatic embryogenesis. *Frontiers in*
1024 *Plant Science* 5, 123838.

- 1025 Su, Y.H., Zhao, X.Y., Liu, Y.B., Zhang, C.L., O'Neill, S.D., Zhang, X.S., 2009. Auxin-induced
1026 WUS expression is essential for embryonic stem cell renewal during somatic embryogenesis in
1027 Arabidopsis. *Plant J* 59, 448-460.
- 1028 Szécsi, J., Joly, C., Bordji, K., Varaud, E., Cock, J.M., Dumas, C., Bendahmane, M., 2006.
1029 BIGPETALp, a bHLH transcription factor is involved in the control of Arabidopsis petal size.
1030 *The EMBO journal* 25, 3912-3920.
- 1031 Szyrajew, K., Bielewicz, D., Dolata, J., Wójcik, A.M., Nowak, K., Szczygieł-Sommer, A.,
1032 Szweykowska-Kulinska, Z., Jarmolowski, A., Gaj, M.D., 2017. MicroRNAs Are Intensively
1033 Regulated during Induction of Somatic Embryogenesis in Arabidopsis. *Front Plant Sci* 8, 18.
- 1034 Tanaka, M., Kikuchi, A., Kamada, H., 2008. The Arabidopsis histone deacetylases HDA6 and
1035 HDA19 contribute to the repression of embryonic properties after germination. *Plant Physiology*
1036 146, 149-161.
- 1037 Thakare, D., Tang, W., Hill, K., Perry, S.E., 2008. The MADS-domain transcriptional regulator
1038 AGAMOUS-LIKE15 promotes somatic embryo development in Arabidopsis and soybean. *Plant*
1039 *Physiology* 146, 1663-1672.
- 1040 Thellin, O., Zorzi, W., Lakaye, B., De Borman, B., Coumans, B., Hennen, G., Grisar, T., Igout,
1041 A., Heinen, E., 1999. Housekeeping genes as internal standards: use and limits. *Journal of*
1042 *Biotechnology* 75, 291-295.
- 1043 Thibaud-Nissen, F., Shealy, R.T., Khanna, A., Vodkin, L.O., 2003. Clustering of microarray data
1044 reveals transcript patterns associated with somatic embryogenesis in soybean. *Plant Physiol* 132,
1045 118-136.
- 1046 Tsugafune, S., Mashiguchi, K., Fukui, K., Takebayashi, Y., Nishimura, T., Sakai, T., Shimada,
1047 Y., Kasahara, H., Koshiba, T., Hayashi, K.-i., 2017. Yucasin DF, a potent and persistent inhibitor
1048 of auxin biosynthesis in plants. *Scientific Reports* 7, 13992.
- 1049 Tvorogova, V.E., Fedorova, Y.A., Potsenkovskaya, E.A., Kudriashov, A.A., Efremova, E.P.,
1050 Kvitkovskaya, V.A., Wolabu, T.W., Zhang, F., Tadege, M., Lutova, L.A., 2019. The
1051 WUSCHEL-related homeobox transcription factor MtWOX9-1 stimulates somatic

- 1052 embryogenesis in *Medicago truncatula*. *Plant Cell, Tissue and Organ Culture (PCTOC)* 138, 517-
1053 527.
- 1054 Uc-Chuc, M.A., Pérez-Hernández, C., Galaz-Ávalos, R.M., Brito-Argaez, L., Aguilar-Hernández,
1055 V., Loyola-Vargas, V.M., 2020. YUCCA-Mediated Biosynthesis of the Auxin IAA Is Required
1056 during the Somatic Embryogenic Induction Process in *Coffea canephora*. *Int J Mol Sci* 21.
- 1057 Varaud, E., Brioude, F., Szécsi, J., Leroux, J., Brown, S., Perrot-Rechenmann, C., Bendahmane,
1058 M., 2011. AUXIN RESPONSE FACTOR8 regulates Arabidopsis petal growth by interacting
1059 with the bHLH transcription factor BIGPETALp. *Plant Cell* 23, 973-983.
- 1060 Wang, F.X., Shang, G.D., Wu, L.Y., Xu, Z.G., Zhao, X.Y., Wang, J.W., 2020. Chromatin
1061 Accessibility Dynamics and a Hierarchical Transcriptional Regulatory Network Structure for
1062 Plant Somatic Embryogenesis. *Dev Cell* 54, 742-757.e748.
- 1063 Wickramasuriya, A.M., Dunwell, J.M., 2015. Global scale transcriptome analysis of Arabidopsis
1064 embryogenesis in vitro. *BMC Genomics* 16, 301.
- 1065 Wójcik, A.M., Wójcikowska, B., Gaj, M.D., 2020. Current Perspectives on the Auxin-Mediated
1066 Genetic Network that Controls the Induction of Somatic Embryogenesis in Plants. *Int J Mol Sci*
1067 21.
- 1068 Wójcikowska, B., Belaidi, S., Robert, H.S., 2023. Game of thrones among AUXIN RESPONSE
1069 FACTORS—over 30 years of MONOPTEROS research. *Journal of Experimental Botany* 74,
1070 6904-6921.
- 1071 Wójcikowska, B., Botor, M., Morończyk, J., Wójcik, A.M., Nodzyński, T., Karcz, J., Gaj, M.D.,
1072 2018. Trichostatin A Triggers an Embryogenic Transition in Arabidopsis Explants via an Auxin-
1073 Related Pathway. *Front Plant Sci* 9, 1353.
- 1074 Wójcikowska, B., Gaj, M.D., 2015. LEAFY COTYLEDON2-mediated control of the
1075 endogenous hormone content: implications for the induction of somatic embryogenesis in
1076 Arabidopsis. *Plant Cell, Tissue and Organ Culture (PCTOC)* 121, 255-258.

- 1077 Wójcikowska, B., Gaj, M.D., 2017. Expression profiling of AUXIN RESPONSE FACTOR
1078 genes during somatic embryogenesis induction in Arabidopsis. *Plant Cell Rep* 36, 843-858.
- 1079 Wójcikowska, B., Jaskóła, K., Gąsiorek, P., Meus, M., Nowak, K., Gaj, M.D., 2013. LEAFY
1080 COTYLEDON2 (LEC2) promotes embryogenic induction in somatic tissues of Arabidopsis, via
1081 YUCCA-mediated auxin biosynthesis. *Planta* 238, 425-440.
- 1082 Wu, L.Y., Shang, G.D., Wang, F.X., Gao, J., Wan, M.C., Xu, Z.G., Wang, J.W., 2022. Dynamic
1083 chromatin state profiling reveals regulatory roles of auxin and cytokinin in shoot regeneration.
1084 *Dev Cell* 57, 526-542.e527.
- 1085 Wu, M.F., Yamaguchi, N., Xiao, J., Bargmann, B., Estelle, M., Sang, Y., Wagner, D., 2015.
1086 Auxin-regulated chromatin switch directs acquisition of flower primordium founder fate. *Elife* 4,
1087 e09269.
- 1088 Xie, M., Huang, L., Song, L., O'Neil, R., Lewsey, M., Chen, H., Chen, H., Zhuo, R., Shokhirev,
1089 M., Alonso, J., Ecker, J., 2022. Defining in vivo transcriptional responses to auxin. *Research*
1090 *Square*.
- 1091 Xu, C., Shen, Y., He, F., Fu, X., Yu, H., Lu, W., Li, Y., Li, C., Fan, D., Wang, H.C., 2019.
1092 Auxin-mediated Aux/IAA-ARF-HB signaling cascade regulates secondary xylem
1093 development in *Populus*. *New Phytologist* 222, 752-767.
- 1094 Xu, L., Liu, Y., Zhang, J., Wu, W., Hao, Z., He, S., Li, Y., Shi, J., Chen, J., 2024. Genomic
1095 survey and expression analysis of LcARFs reveal multiple functions to somatic embryogenesis in
1096 *Liriodendron*. *BMC Plant Biology* 24, 94.
- 1097 Yang, X., Lin, Q., Udayabhanu, J., Hua, Y., Dai, X., Xin, S., Wang, X., Huang, H., Huang, T.,
1098 2024. An optimized somatic embryo transformation system assisted homozygous edited rubber
1099 tree generation method mediated by CRISPR/Cas9. *bioRxiv*, 2024.2003. 2014.585007.
- 1100 Yue, P., Lu, Q., Liu, Z., Lv, T., Li, X., Bu, H., Liu, W., Xu, Y., Yuan, H., Wang, A., 2020.
1101 Auxin-activated MdARF5 induces the expression of ethylene biosynthetic genes to initiate apple
1102 fruit ripening. *New phytologist* 226, 1781-1795.

1103 Zeng, J., Deng, Y., Iqbal, S., Zhang, J., Wu, K., Ma, G., Li, L., Dai, G., Deng, R., Fang, L., Zeng,
1104 S., 2024. Direct somatic embryogenesis and related gene expression networks in leaf explants of
1105 *Hippeastrum* 'Bangkok Rose'. *Horticultural Plant Journal* 10, 556-572.

1106 Zhang, M.M., Zhang, H.K., Zhai, J.F., Zhang, X.S., Sang, Y.L., Cheng, Z.J., 2021. ARF4
1107 regulates shoot regeneration through coordination with ARF5 and IAA12. *Plant Cell Rep* 40,
1108 315-325.

1109 Zheng, Q., Perry, S.E., 2014. Alterations in the transcriptome of soybean in response to enhanced
1110 somatic embryogenesis promoted by orthologs of *Agamous-like15* and *Agamous-like18*. *Plant*
1111 *Physiol* 164, 1365-1377.

1112 Zheng, Y., Ren, N., Wang, H., Stromberg, A.J., Perry, S.E., 2009. Global identification of targets
1113 of the *Arabidopsis* MADS domain protein *AGAMOUS-Like15*. *The Plant Cell* 21, 2563-2577.

1114 Zhu, X., Xu, Z., Wang, G., Cong, Y., Yu, L., Jia, R., Qin, Y., Zhang, G., Li, B., Yuan, D., Tu, L.,
1115 Yang, X., Lindsey, K., Zhang, X., Jin, S., 2023. Single-cell resolution analysis reveals the
1116 preparation for reprogramming the fate of stem cell niche in cotton lateral meristem. *Genome*
1117 *Biol* 24, 194.

1118

1119 **Figure legend**

1120 **Figure 1. *MP11ir* and *MP* are expressed during somatic embryogenesis induction.**

1121 (A) The level of *MP11ir* transcript in IZE explants and during auxin-dependent (5.0 μ M 2,4-D)
1122 SE induction (5th and 10th day of *in vitro* culture). Values significantly different from the control
1123 culture (10-day-old seedlings) are marked with asterisks. The relative expression level was
1124 normalized to internal control (*At4g27090*) and calibrated to the 10-day-old seedling. A two-way
1125 ANOVA analysis ($p < 0.05$) followed by Tukey's HSD was used to determine any values that
1126 were significantly different from 10-day-old seedlings ($*p < 0.05$; $**p < 0.01$) ($n = 3$; means \pm
1127 SD are presented). (B-P) The level of *MP11ir* transcript in the IZE explants cultured for ten days
1128 on medium without exogenous auxin, control condition (E, I, M), and treated with 2,4-D (B),
1129 NAA (C) and IAA (D) concentrations of 2.5 (F, J, N), 5.0 (G, K, O), and 7.5 μ M (H, L, P).
1130 Values significantly different from the control culture (explants untreated with 2,4-D, NAA, or

1131 IAA) are marked with asterisks. The relative expression level was calibrated to the 10-day-old
1132 IZE control culture untreated with exogenous auxin. A two-way ANOVA analysis ($p < 0.05$)
1133 followed by Tukey's HSD was used to determine any values that were significantly different
1134 from untreated IZE explants ($*p < 0.05$; $**p < 0.01$) ($n = 3$; means \pm SD are presented). Size bars
1135 indicate 1 mm (**E-P**). (**Q**) The *MP11ir* transcript level in IZE explants and during TSA-dependent
1136 (1.0 μ M TSA) SE induction (5th and 10th day of *in vitro* culture). Values significantly different
1137 from the control culture (10-day-old seedlings) are marked with asterisks. A two-way ANOVA
1138 analysis ($p < 0.05$) followed by Tukey's HSD was used to determine any values that were
1139 significantly different from 10-day-old seedlings ($*p < 0.05$; $**p < 0.01$) ($n = 3$; means \pm SD are
1140 presented). (**R**) Together with data presented in Supplementary Figure S2, we hypothesize a
1141 positive correlation between *MP11ir* levels and SE capacity. (**S-U**) The level of *MP* transcript in
1142 the IZE explants cultured on medium without exogenous auxin and treated with 2,4-D (**S**), NAA
1143 (**T**), and IAA (**U**) concentrations of 2.5, 5.0, and 7.5 μ M. Values significantly different from the
1144 control culture (explants untreated with 2,4-D, NAA, or IAA) are marked with asterisks. The
1145 relative expression level was calibrated to the 10-day-old IZE control culture untreated with
1146 exogenous auxin. A two-way ANOVA analysis ($p < 0.05$) followed by Tukey's HSD was used to
1147 determine any values that were significantly different from untreated IZE explants ($*p < 0.05$;
1148 $**p < 0.01$) ($n \geq 3$; means \pm SD are presented). (**V, W**) The expression profile of *MP* in IZE
1149 explants and during auxin-dependent (5.0 μ M 2,4-D) (**V**) and TSA-dependent (1.0 μ M TSA) (**W**)
1150 SE induction (5th and 10th days of *in vitro* culture). Values significantly different from the
1151 expression 10-day-old seedlings are marked with asterisks. A two-way ANOVA analysis ($p <$
1152 0.05) followed by Tukey's HSD was used to determine any values that were significantly
1153 different from 10-day-old seedlings ($*p < 0.05$; $**p < 0.01$) ($n \geq 3$; means \pm SD are presented).
1154 (**X**) The expression profile of *MP* during auxin-dependent (E5) and TSA-dependent (ET) SE
1155 induction (5th and 10th days of *in vitro* culture). The relative expression level was calibrated to the
1156 *MP11ir* expression on the same day of *in vitro* culture. Values significantly different from the
1157 *MP11ir* expression are marked with asterisks. A two-way ANOVA analysis ($p < 0.05$) followed
1158 by Tukey's HSD was used to determine any values that were significantly different from 10-day-
1159 old seedlings ($*p < 0.05$; $**p < 0.01$) ($n \geq 3$; means \pm SD are presented). (**Y**) The transcript level
1160 of *MP* and *MP11ir* during the auxin (E5) and TSA-dependent (ET) SE process (5th and 10th days
1161 of *in vitro* culture). The expression level was calculated using the 40- Δ Ct method. The

1162 At4g27090 gene was used as internal control and for normalization. Values significantly different
1163 from the expression of *MP* are marked with asterisks. A two-way ANOVA analysis ($p < 0.05$)
1164 followed by Tukey's HSD was used to determine any values that were significantly different
1165 from *MP* expression ($*p < 0.05$; $**p < 0.01$) ($n \geq 3$; means \pm SD are presented). (Z) The location
1166 of primers used to detect *MP* transcript is indicated.

1167
1168 **Figure 2. MP and MP11ir are both required to rescue the reduced SE capacity of *mpS319*.**
1169 (A-M) The embryogenic capacity (A, B) of the Col-0 (C, H), *mpS319* mutant (D, I, J),
1170 *pMP::MP11ir* (E, K), *pMP::MP* (F, L) and *pMP::MP11ir pMP::MP* (G, M) transgenes in
1171 *mpS319* background on the E5 medium evaluated in a 21-day-old culture. Values significantly
1172 different from the control culture (Col-0) are marked with asterisks, and from *mpS319* mutant are
1173 marked with hashtags. A two-way ANOVA analysis ($p < 0.05$) followed by Tukey's HSD was
1174 used to determine any values that were significantly different ($*^{\#}p < 0.05$; $**^{\#\#}p < 0.01$) ($n \geq 3$;
1175 means \pm SD are given). (N-X) The embryogenic capacity (N, O) of the Col-0 (P, S, V),
1176 *p35S::bdl-GR* (Q, T, W), *p35S::BDL-GR* (R, U, X) transgenic lines on the E5 medium (P, Q, R)
1177 and E5 medium supplemented with 10 μ M (S, T, U) and 30 μ M (V, W, X) of DEX. SE capacity
1178 was evaluated in 21-day-old cultures. Values significantly different from the control culture (Col-
1179 0) untreated with DEX are marked with asterisks. A two-way ANOVA analysis ($p < 0.05$)
1180 followed by Tukey's HSD was used to determine any values that were significantly different ($*p$
1181 < 0.05 ; $**p < 0.01$) ($n = 3$; means \pm SD are presented). Size bars indicate 1 mm for explant
1182 images and 1 cm for plate images.

1183
1184 **Figure 3. Expression pattern of MP and MP11ir during SE induction**
1185 Spatio-temporal localization of MP (A) and MP11ir (B) in IZE explants and explants cultured on
1186 the SE induction medium with 5 μ M 2,4-D by 1 (C, D), 5 (E, F) and 10 (G, H) days of SE
1187 culture. d, day of SE culture. IZE explants were cultured from *pMP::MP-GFP* (A, C, E, G) and
1188 *pMP::MP11ir-GFP* (B, D, F, H) transgenic lines. The GFP fluorescence is shown in green. The
1189 blue fluorescence marks the cell (Renaissance staining). (A-H 1-4) Magnification views of the
1190 areas marked in A-H. Size bars indicate 200 μ m (A-F), 20 μ m (A-H1-4).

1191
1192 **Figure 4. Overexpressing *ΔARF5* impairs SE induction**

1193 (A, B) The embryogenic capacity of *pXVE::ΔARF5 pDR5::GFP* explants treated with different
1194 2,4-D concentrations was evaluated in a 21-day-old culture. The significantly impaired SE
1195 efficiency (A) and productivity (B) of the *ΔARF5*-expressing explants are presented. (C) Explants
1196 overexpressing *ΔARF5* and cultured on auxin-media could not regenerate somatic embryos and
1197 produced callus. *ΔARF5* overexpression was induced with 1 μM estradiol (+E). Values
1198 significantly different from the control culture (Col-0) are marked with asterisks. A two-way
1199 ANOVA analysis ($p < 0.05$) followed by Tukey's HSD was used to determine any values that
1200 were significantly different ($*p < 0.05$) ($n = 3$; means \pm SD are given). Size bars indicate 1 mm
1201 for explant images and 1 cm for plate images.

1202
1203 **Figure 5. *TAA1*, *TAR1*, *YUC3*, *YUC5*, and *YUC8* expression levels are altered when MP-**
1204 **dependent transcriptional activities are impaired.**

1205 (A-F) Relative expression level of *TAA1*, *TAR1*, *YUC3*, *YUC5*, and *YUC8* auxin biosynthetic
1206 genes in the 1- (A), 5- (B), and 10-day-old (C) embryogenic cultures of the *pXVE::ΔARF5*
1207 *pDR5::GFP* transgenic line treated with 1 μM β-estradiol (+E), 5- and 10-day-old embryogenic
1208 cultures of the *p35S::bdl-GR* transgenic line treated with 10 μM dexamethasone (+DEX) (D), and
1209 0- (E) and 10-day-old (F) embryogenic cultures of *mp* mutant, (G, H). Relative expression level
1210 of *TAA1*, *TAR1*, *YUC3*, *YUC5*, and *YUC8* auxin biosynthetic genes in 5- (G) and 10-day-old (H)
1211 embryogenic cultures of *mp* mutant, *pMP::MP mpS319*, *pMP::MP11ir mpS319*, and
1212 *pMP::MP11ir pMP::MP mpS319*. The relative expression level was normalized to internal
1213 control (At4g27090) and calibrated to the *pXVE::ΔARF5 pDR5::GFP* culture of the same age
1214 and untreated with 1 μM β-estradiol (-E) (A-C) or *p35S::bdl-GR* culture of the same age and
1215 untreated with 10 μM dexamethasone (-DEX) (D), or Col-0 embryogenic culture of the same age
1216 (E, F, G). Values significantly different from the *pXVE::ΔARF5 pDR5::GFP* (-E) (A-C),
1217 *p35S::bdl-GR* (-DEX) (D) or Col-0 (E, F) culture of the same age are marked with asterisks ($*p$
1218 < 0.05 ; $n = 3 \pm$ SD). Values significantly different from the Col-0 culture of the same age are
1219 marked with asterisks (*), *arf5* are marked with hashtags (#), *pMP::MP mpS319* are marked with
1220 carets (^), *pMP::MP11ir mpS319* are marked with dollar sign (\$), *pMP::MP11ir pMP::MP*
1221 *mpS319* are marked with ampersands (&) (G). ($*\#\^{\$}\& p < 0.05$; $n = 3 \pm$ SD).

1222 **Figure 6. *TAA1*, *TAR1*, *YUC3*, *YUC5*, and *YUC8* expression patterns are altered when MP-**
1223 **dependent transcriptional activities are impaired.**

1224 Spatio-temporal localization of TAA1, TAR1, YUC3, YUC5, and YUC8 enzymes during SE
1225 process under *in vitro* culture in *pXVE::ΔARF5 pDR5::GFP* (A) *p35S::bdl-GR* (B) or *mp*
1226 background (C). IZE explants of reporter lines were cultured on an E5 medium as a control (A,
1227 B, C), E5 medium with 1 μM β-estradiol for *ΔARF5* overexpression (+E) (A), E5 medium with
1228 10 μM dexamethasone (+DEX) (B). The tissue was sampled on the 5- and 10-day-old *in vitro*
1229 cultures (A, B), and in IZEs, explants on the 5- and 10-day-old *in vitro* cultures (C). The
1230 expression is visible in blue from *pTAA1::TAA1-GUS*, *pTAR1::TAR1-GUS*, *pYUC3::YUC3-GUS*,
1231 *pYUC5::YUC5-GUS*, and *pYUC8::YUC8-GUS* reporter lines crossed into the respective genetic
1232 backgrounds. Size bars indicate 200 μm.

1233
1234 **Figure 7.** Summary of the localization of TAA1 (A), TAR1 (B), YUC3 (C), YUC5 (D), and
1235 YUC8 (E) enzymes during SE process under *in vitro* culture of Col-0, *pXVE::ΔARF5*
1236 *pDR5::GFP* line treated with β-estradiol, *p35S::bdl-GR* line treated with DEX, and *mp* mutant.

1237
1238 **Figure 8. Overexpressing *ΔARF5* increases endogenous auxin levels.**
1239 (A-D) GFP-monitored auxin maxima in *pXVE::ΔARF5 pDR5::GFP* explants cultured for 1 (A,
1240 B) and 5 days (C, D) on an ET medium (1.0 μM TSA) without (-E) (A, C) or with β-estradiol
1241 (+E) (B, D). The GFP fluorescence signal is displayed in green. (E, F) The fluorescence signal
1242 was quantified in 1- (E) and 5-day-old (F) explants. (G) Level of indolic compounds (μg/g of
1243 fresh tissue) in 3-week-old IZE-culture of *pXVE::ΔARF5 pDR5::GFP* cultures with 1 μM β-
1244 estradiol to induce *ΔARF5* overexpression. (H) Level of IAA (ng/g of dry weight DW) in 10-day-
1245 old IZE-culture of *pXVE::ΔARF5 pDR5::GFP* with 1 μM β-estradiol to induce *ΔARF5*
1246 overexpression. A two-way ANOVA analysis ($p < 0.05$) followed by Tukey's HSD was used to
1247 determine any values that were significantly different ($*p < 0.05$; $**p < 0.01$). Size bars indicate
1248 200 μm (A-D) and 1 mm (G). Arrowhead (A, C) marked regions of high auxin response in
1249 *pXVE::ΔARF5 pDR5::GFP* explants untreated by β-estradiol (-E).

1250 **Figure 9. Proposed model of MP and MP11ir action during embryogenic transition through**
1251 **control of auxin-biosynthesis genes expression.** (A) The canonical MP protein and MP11ir
1252 isoform are required for the efficient embryogenic transition by controlling auxin biosynthesis
1253 genes. (B) Overexpression of a truncated *ΔARF5* protein, caused elevated level of TAA1, YUC3,
1254 YUC5, and YUC8 enzymes in explants, which disrupts auxin homeostasis, leads to suboptimal

1255 endogenous auxin levels, inhibits the SE process, and induces the formation of callus. (C)
1256 Blocking MP action through the expression of the *bd1* repressor results in decreased TAA1,
1257 YUC3, YUC5 and YUC8 levels during SE induction, inhibits the SE process, and induces
1258 seedling development. (D) The lack of MP and MP11ir in *mp* mutant leads to the decreased
1259 TAA1 level, absence of YUC3, YUC5, and YUC8 enzymes during early stage of SE induction
1260 what inhibits the SE process, and leads to callus formation. AuxRE – Auxin Response Elements;
1261 BRM/SYD – BRAHMA/SPLAYED; MP – MONOPTEROS; MP11ir – MP isoform; TFs -
1262 TRANSCRIPTION FACTOR; HAT – HISTONE ACETYLASES; TAA1 - TRYPTOPHAN
1263 AMINOTRANSFERASE OF ARABIDOPSIS 1, TAR1 - TRYPTOPHAN
1264 AMINOTRANSFERASE RELATED 1; TPL/TPR – TOPLESS/TPL-RELATED; YUC –
1265 YUCCA; Ac – acetyl group; SE – somatic embryogenesis. Created with BioRender.com.

1266

pMP::MP-GFP

pMP::MP11ir-GFP

0 day

1 day

5 day

10 day

<https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.07.17.603838>

This preprint (which was not certified by peer review) is the author/funder, who has granted bioRxiv a license to display the preprint in perpetuity. It is made available under aCC-BY 4.0 International license.

bioRxiv preprint doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.07.17.603838>; this version posted May 7, 2025. The copyright holder for this preprint (which was not certified by peer review) is the author/funder, who has granted bioRxiv a license to display the preprint in perpetuity. It is made available under aCC-BY 4.0 International license.